

3rd ICIGR 2021

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INTELLECTUALS' GLOBAL RESPONSIBILITY AND CALL FOR PAPER'S

SCIENCE AND RESEARCH IN THE POST PANDEMIC ERA FOR IMPROVING PUBLIC WELFARE

HELD DATE : 7 DECEMBER 2021

Opening Speech ICIGR 2021

The issue of public welfare is currently a central global issue, given the impact of the prolonged COVID-19 pandemic affecting the economic and social conditions of the community. Social restrictions or lockdown policies imposed by many countries certainly affect industrial productivity and people's purchasing power. The surge in COVID-19 cases in several developed countries, especially in Europe and the US, affected the demand and supply of goods, which resulted in the decline of the global economy. At this time, a new issue has emerged regarding the Omicron variant which is considered more destructive than the delta variant which dominates Covid cases in many countries today, although the WHO later gave a bit of relief that there have been no reports of deaths from 40 countries that have been attacked by Omicron.

Many countries have responded to this pandemic by refocusing their budgets to deal with COVID-19 so that the economic development of many countries is hampered. However, some of the government's policies to carry out a lockdown and strict social restrictions on the spread of COVID-19 cases were responded by its citizens with anarchic actions, as happened recently in Brussels, Belgium. The re-enactment of the lockdown with various current conditions is considered less able to facilitate the needs of the community to be more prosperous. They want the freedom to work and do activities in order to gain psychological and economic well-being. Of course, we do not want the decline in welfare and social conflicts to occur in our country.

In addition, complete vaccination programs and the application of health protocols remain the main policies in several countries, especially in Indonesia to prevent the spread and severity of COVID-19 while slowly opening the economy taps through the opening of various facilities and public transportation such as malls and recreation areas. This policy turned out to be quite effective in controlling the current rate of COVID-19 in Indonesia and increasing the economic growth rate to be positive.

On the other hand, the presence of a pandemic is recognized as sharpening technological developments. The virality of video conferencing, e-commerce, software collaboration, cloud, IoT, and the emergence of new terms such as work from home and distance learning indicate that our ecosystem will be different from before the pandemic, even if the pandemic ends life will never be the same.

Therefore, academics from various campuses and countries who are gathered in this ICGR, who come from Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, and the Philippines, have a strategic role to produce knowledge, concepts, strategies, and technology that are able to become solutions to problems that arise. problems that occur in society. Collaboration between researchers across universities is also very much needed to ensure that what we are doing today is effective, efficient and has a massive impact that is beneficial for improving the welfare of the community.

Ekohardi Ansyah
Vice Chancellor
Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo

RUNDOWN 3rd ICIGR 2021

International Conference on Intellectuals Global Responsibility

Tema: **“Science and Research in the Post Pandemic Era for Improving Public Welfare”**

7 Desember 2021

No.	Program	Time	Detail Program	PIC
1.	Opening Ceremony	08.00-08.25	Registration	Committee
		08.25-08.28	Opening Ceremony	MC (Rani)
		08.28-08.35	Pembacaan ayat suci Al-Qur'an	Qori (Syakar)
	08.25-09.00	08.35-08.40	Welcome speech by Direktur Direktorat Riset dan Pengabdian Masyarakat (DRPM) Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo Dr. Sigit Hermawan	MC
		08.40-08.50	Opening speech ICIGR 2021 by Rector, Dr. Hidayatulloh, M.Si	
		08.50-08.55	The signing of Memorandum of Agreement with the CoHost of ICIGR Institut Teknologi and Bisnis Ahmad Dahlan Lamongan	
		08.55-09.00	Welcome speech from Cohost by Rector of the Institute of Technology and Business Ahmad Dahlan Lamongan, Dr. Mu'ah, M.M., M.Pd.	
2.	PANEL Session 1	09.00-09.30	Assoc. Prof. Pensri Jaroenwanit Ph.D The Dean of Faculty of Business Administration and Accountancy, Khon Kaen University Thailand	Wahyu Taufiq, M.Ed
		09.30-10.00	Assoc Prof. Dr. Yahya Don The Dean of School of Education (SOE), University Utara Malaysia	
		10.00-10.30	Question and Answer	
3.	PANEL Session 2	10.30-11.00	Prof. Sema D Gilna, Ed.D The president of Cotabato State University, Phillipine	Wahyu Taufiq, M.Ed
		11.00-11.30	Dr. Rahmania Sri Untari, M.Pd Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo, Indonesia	
		11.30-12.00	Question and Answer	
4.	Closing	12.00-12.05	Closing statement	MC

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[AR-0200]

**Arabic Education Marketing Strategy Model During The COVID-19
Pandemic Based On Networking**

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Abstract

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic is a challenge for the marketing of Arabic language educational institutions. Implementing Arabic language learning as the main product that requires interaction and practice offline is forced to change online. This study aims to determine the marketing strategy model of networking-based Arabic educational institutions attracting public interest during the COVID-19 pandemic. Several previous research results have been synthesized for overviewing the education marketing strategy based on networking. A systematic Literature Review has been carried out by documenting and reviewing all articles related to education marketing in 2016-2021. This study has used 25 national and international journal articles accessed from Lens.org, Sinta, Google Scholar, Science Direct, and DOAJ. The results of the literature study state that the Arabic education marketing strategy model during the COVID-19 pandemic based on networking is carried out by 1. Implementing of managerial marketing strategy includes SWOT analysis, planning, team organizing, implementing, and monitoring marketing results 2. They were implementing of marketing mix digitally 3. Optimization of network marketing. Network marketing is needed for direct marketing to be more effective, accessible, and on target so that public interest in Arabic language education is expected to increase.

Keyword : marketing strategy, COVID-19 pandemic, networking

Subject :

[AR-0303]

The Influence Of Instructional Leadership And Change Leadership On School Achievement

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the effect of instructional leadership (X1), change leadership (X2) on school achievement (Y). This study used quantitative methods. Data collected through questionnaires and documents. The study sample consisted of 91 teachers and 21 schools. Data was analysed by multiple regression analysis. The results showed a significant influence on the variables of instructional leadership (X1), change leadership (X2) on school achievement (Y) with a regression coefficient of 0.718. The regression equation form is: $\hat{Y} = 52.71 + 0.519 X_1 + 0.718 X_2$. Effective contribution of instructional leadership variables (X1), change leadership (X2), and to the school achievement (Y) was 30,22 %.

Keyword : instructional leadership, change leadership, school achievement.

Subject :

[AR-0234]

Remodelling Of Character Education In School In The New Normal Post-pandemic Covid-19 Era

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Abstract

This paper presents the remodelling of character education in the new normal post-pandemic covid-19 era. During the pandemic, the learning processes used an online system to reduce the spread of the covid-19 virus. This condition made the character education process ineffective and caused the loss of student character values. To solve this problem, schools must use technology to optimize the learning process in character education. This study aimed to determine the effective character education models for schools to face the new normal era. Using the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method, this research focused on finding character education models effective and applied at school. The literature review results showed that character education models are effective: first, character education models through habituation in daily activities at school and home. Second, character education models integrate with the learning process and extracurricular activities. Third, character education models used digital media. All character education models above have used hybrid systems combining offline and online systems to deliver character values to students. By this research, remodelling of character education can improve the effectiveness of the character education process in schools to face the new normal post-pandemic era.

Keyword : remodelling, character education, new normal, post-pandemic

Subject :

[AR-0243]

Transformation Of Learning Input Factors In The New Normal Era Post-Covid-19

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Abstract

Learning is a process that involves a system. Learning as a system has three main components, namely, input, process, and output. The Covid-19 pandemic has changed the global system in the world and forced it to adapt to current conditions, including learning. Learning in the new normal era must adjust to conditions after the Covid-19 pandemic so as not to reduce the quality of learning. This study aims to examine the literature related to input factors in learning in the new normal era after the Covid-19 pandemic. The SLR (Systematic Literature Review) method has been carried out by documenting and reviewing some articles with keyword learning and the Covid-19 pandemic in the 2018-2021 period. The articles used in this study were 17 accredited national and international journal articles accessed from SINTA, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect. The study of this article presents learning input factors that focus on instrumental input namely, curriculum, teaching materials, educator competencies, facilities and infrastructure, learning media and learning evaluation. This study indicates that there is a transformation of facilities and infrastructure, curriculum, learning media, and educator competencies in learning activities to achieve learning outcomes in the new normal era.

Keyword : Transformation, instrumental input, learning, new normal era

Subject :

[AR-0225]

The Effectiveness Of Teacher Professionalism In Improving The Quality Of Learning

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-

Abstract

Efforts to increase teacher professionalism in the world of education are the first steps that must be taken to improve the quality of the learning process. The teacher's role is expected to create an education that frees people from adversity, poverty, and various crises that are engulfing all elements of the nation. The article is the result of a literature review that aims to determine the effectiveness of teacher professionalism in improving the quality of learning. The method used in this study uses an SLR (Systematic Literature Review) approach, namely research to identify, evaluate, and interpret all relevant research results related to certain research questions. The results of a systematic literature review of 15 journal articles on teacher professionalism in improving the quality of learning, the results show that the aspect of teacher professionalism has a strong enough dominance in improving the quality of learning in the classroom, namely the domain of the teacher's ability to prepare lesson plans, the quality of learning implementation and providing evaluations. learning.

Keyword : Professionalism, Teacher, Quality, Learning

Subject :

[AR-0209]

**Principal Democratic Leadership In Increasing Creativity Islamic
Religious Education Teacher**

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

The emergence of the Covid-19 outbreak has made the education system start looking for innovations for the process of teaching and learning activities. Moreover, Circular no. 4 th 2020 from the Minister of Education and culture who recommends that all activities in educational institutions must keep a distance and deliver material at their respective homes. Every institution is required to provide the latest innovations to form a very effective learning process. Unfortunately, not all educational institutions seem to understand very well about the latest innovations that must be used to carry out learning during the pandemic. Most of them are still unable to adjust it due to inadequate facilities and infrastructure. This requires the creativity of a teacher for school success factors, especially regarding the creativity of Islamic Religious Education teachers who experience many obstacles in the teaching process during the pandemic, because teaching is not enough to convey material but requires a student approach directly related to student behavior. From previous research, using the Systematic Literature Review Method on the lens.org, DOAJ and sciencedirect.com sites, several studies have been found that provide an overview of democratic leadership and the creativity of a teacher. In order for learning to be effective again during this pandemic, we need methods such as Project Based Learning, Online Method, Offline Method, Home Visit Method, Integrated Curriculum, Blended Learning, so that learning can be effective again although not 100% before the Covid_19 outbreak.

Keyword : Democratic Leadership; Teacher Creativity

Subject :

[AR-0263]

School Marketing Strategy During The Covid-19 Pandemic
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Sidoarjo), (AC-1183 Renny Oktafia /

Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo), (AC-1184 Eni Fariyatul Fahyuni /
Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo),

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UNIVERSITAS MUHAMMADIYAH SIDOARJO

Abstract

Many sectors of life have been affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, including the school marketing sector. Managers of educational institutions were challenged to make reforms in marketing schools to the community. School marketing was essential to provide information about school products. The problem with this research was that school marketing could not meet prospective students directly because of the pandemic. Therefore, a school marketing strategy was needed that could increase public interest. This study aimed to conduct a literature review related to school marketing strategies during the COVID-19 pandemic. The method chosen in this study is the SLR (Systematic Literature Review) method. A Systematic Literature Review has been conducted by reviewing all articles related to school marketing strategies for 2016–2021. The articles used in this study were 25 national and international accredited journal articles accessed from Science Direct, DOAJ, and Lens.org. The literature review of journal articles resulted in strategies, namely: (1) development of excellent school programs; (2) utilization of internet media as a school promotion channel; and (3) establishing an effective relationship between the school and parents of students.

Keyword : Covid-19 pandemic, marketing strategy, school

Subject :

[AR-0216]

Website-based Child-friendly Madrasah E-learning During The Covid-19 Pandemic

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

Website-based madrasa e-learning is a child-friendly platform for online learning activities that are free, user-friendly and has full features compared to other platforms. The COVID-19 pandemic that has hit the world has had a tremendous impact on education. The government has established an online learning system at all levels of education. Digital media is an essential source for student learning activities, but its use that is not limited and easily accessible can cause disadvantageous effects, especially for elementary school children. So that educational institutions must be precise in determining online learning platforms that are child-friendly and suitable for teachers and parents accompanying students. Using the Systematic Literature Review method from national and international accredited journal articles accessed from SINTA, DOAJ, Scimago, lens.org and Scopus can document and review all articles related to online learning applications for the 2015-2021 period. The results of the literature review of this research article indicate that existing online learning applications only facilitate children's learning needs without paying attention to the emergence of features that are not following child development, especially at elementary school age. Even educators must follow existing applications without being able to develop creativity and innovation in learning. With website-based madrasa elearning, madrasa can apply teacher design to support the teaching and learning process to be more structured, innovative, interactive, and exciting for students. Parents are calmer in monitoring and supervising children's learning because all of their children's learning needs are already in it without opening other features.

Keyword : Website-based madrasa e-learning; a child-friendly platform for online learning

Subject

[AR-0230]

The Effectiveness Of Principal Supervision In Improving Teacher Performance

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

The principal has a strategic position in developing school resources, especially in empowering teachers in achieving the educational goals that have been set. This article aims to describe the effectiveness of principal supervision in improving teacher performance. The method used in this study uses an SLR (Systematic Literature Review) approach by identifying, evaluating, and interpreting all relevant research results related to certain research questions, certain topics, or phenomena of concern. The method in searching for data sources for journal articles is carried out through the lens.org website database and Google Scholar. The results obtained illustrate that the supervision of the principal has a very good effectiveness in improving teacher performance. The more dominant aspect lies in 83% academic supervision and 75% clinical supervision.

Keyword : Principal, Supervision, Teacher, Performance

Subject :

[AR-0208]

**Implementation Of Academic Supervision Of The Principal
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Taufik Churrahman / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo),**

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

Supervision is a coaching activity carried out by the principal to assist teachers and other employees in doing their work in the learning process effectively. Supervision is very important because it is a process of supervision activities carried out by the principal to teachers to improve the quality of teaching and learning activities to learners, as well as help teachers in motivating, improving, developing their abilities and potential in the teaching and learning process to be achieved. The research method selected in this study is the SLR (Systematic Literature Review) method. Data collection is done by documenting and reviewing all articles related to Academic Supervision published in the period 2015-2021. The 30 national and international journal articles were obtained from Google Scholar and lens.org site. From scientific reviews found that in Academic Supervision there are still many administrations of teacher learning, there are still learning devices used by teachers adopted and incomplete, the availability of learning facilities are lacking, teachers do not set clear lines and scenarios in the learning process so that the classroom atmosphere becomes less condusive, and also teachers rarely communicate with students more closely, For that, with the supervision of academic principals can improve the administration of teacher learning, and provide motivation and a good way to teach in the future.

Keyword : Academic Supervision, Principal, Teacher

Subject :

[AR-0277]

Model For Strengthening Academic Culture Of Principal Leadership

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

The development of this model was carried out at SD Muhammadiyah 2 Pendil, Probolinggo Regency, to strengthen the academic culture that leads to principal leadership in Islamic education. Development is applied in institutions, educators and students. The product is based on the sociocultural, internal and external environment and applicable policies to shape the character of students and school members under the supervision of the principal as a leader. It is instilling honest character and being able to act pretty in everyday life. This study uses various reference literature that can help researchers in developing academic culture. Because there are still some students who need guidance to make it easier for educators to reinforce with a model of character building for students who are future-minded, in this case, it is hoped that it will produce a generation that is honest, able to adapt to the times and be fair. The long-term hope in this model is to make a robust and intellectual generation in the Koran, has character, and is progressive in facing the future.

Keyword : Academic Culture, Principal Leadership

Subject :

[AR-0218]

Ethno-STEM To Develop Student's Entrepreneurial Characters At Islamic Boarding School

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*Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo), (AC-1512 Eni Fariyatul Fahyuni /
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Abstract

Ethno-STEM to Reduce the Phenomenon of Saturation and Develop Student Entrepreneurial Character. Society 5.0 is a human-centered and technology-based concept through a system that integrates virtual and physical spaces. The world of education is required to continue to innovate. Islamic boarding school is an educational institution that combines religious learning with general learning to effectively educate intelligence, skills, character development and inculcate moral values as a complete and distinctive person without leaving Islamic values. The 24-hour learning system is a source of student learning saturation. The approach used in carrying out active learning and fostering learning motivation is EthnoSTEM. A systematic literature review was done by documenting and reviewing all articles related to active learning in increasing learning motivation during the 2018-2021 period. The articles used are nationally and internationally accredited journals accessed from Science Direct, Google Scholar, SINTA, DOAJ, and Lens. The literature review results of articles on the Ethno-STEM approach can increase students' learning motivation because active learning is carried out and stimulates students to improve thinking skills, especially critical, creative, innovative, and entrepreneurial characters. Several studies show students' interests and talents in entrepreneurial personalities from the middle to high levels to produce innovative products.

Keyword : Ethno-STEM, interest in learning, the phenomenon of saturation, entrepreneurship character,

Subject :

[AR-0250]

**Curriculum Model Of Islamic Boarding School Mu
(AC-1313 Westi Wiliyana sari / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo), (AC-
1314 Yayuk Fauziah / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo),**

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0252 Westi Wiliyana Sari)

Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

The curriculum is generally used as a benchmark for education to produce learners in accordance with national education goals. The curriculum model of mu'allimin and mu'allimat education curriculum is pure autonomy that has no bond of service and any institution is now still surviving to develop and advance in the midst of formal educational institutions or islamic Boarding schools education institutions that now have many advantages (admission) and progress. The research aims to conduct a literature review related to the mu'allimin and mu'allimat curriculum models, 1) understand the curriculum model of mu'allimin and mu'allimat boarding schools, 2) find out how islamic Boarding schools implements islamic Boarding schools education culture with mu'allimin and mu'allimat curriculum models in this modern era. The research method selected in this study is the systematic Literature Review. Data collection is done by documenting and reviewing all articles related to interactive applications published in the period 2016 – 2021. The articles used in this study as many as 30 articles of national and international journals obtained from google scholar and lens.org site. From scientific reviews, it was found that the curriculum is an educational plan that is planned and implemented to achieve educational goals that require innovation and the development of good education. In the era of modernization of the mu'allimin and mu'allimat curriculum models that are comprehensive, systematic, and systematic, it is still a reference for various islamic Boarding schools educations by combining various elements of educational disciplines into a mu'allimin and mu'allimat format that becomes its own excellence and is seen by learners who master Arabic and English skills actively without ruling out religious or general science.

Keyword : Curriculum, Islamic Boarding School, Mu'allimin dan Mu'allimat

[AR-0217]

A Systematic Literature Review: Blended Learning Becomes An Icon Of Elementary School Excellence

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Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo), (AC-1509 Eni Fariyatul Fahyuni / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo),

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SDN JIMBARAN WETAN

Abstract

The covid-19 pandemic in era 4.0 did not discourage education organizers in Indonesia from exploring the uniqueness and excellence of schools. Inter-schools remain competing to show the icon of creative and innovative school excellence in the pandemic covid-19. Large-scale social restrictions cause school organizers to think creatively so that teaching and learning activities run in schools. One of the solutions provided by the school is to carry out blended learning. Blended learning is defined as integrated learning between face-to-face learning and online distance learning or e-learning. This research was conducted to find out whether blended learning can become an icon of school excellence. To answer this has been done systematic literature review by documenting and reviewing all articles related to the combined learning period 2017-2021. The papers used in the study were 20 nationally and internationally accredited journals accessed from Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, and ResearchGate. The results of a literature study of 20 research articles that examine blended learning show that blended learning plays an important role and becomes a solution to teaching and learning activities in the covid-19 pandemic and the 21st century. So blended learning can be an icon of school excellence, but successful blended learning requires alignment of institutional goals, educators, students, and parents.

Keyword : blended learning, school excellence icon

Subject :

[AR-0222]

**Management Of Counseling Guidance Services And Skills Building
For Junior High School Students**

***(AC-1522 Dianita Wahyu Ningsih, Eni Fariyatul Fahyuni / Universitas
Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo),***

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Abstract

Education is the goal to educate and develop the potential in a person. The more growing and developing each individual can have creativity, more expansive knowledge, a good personality, form a good character, and recognize their potential. Character building is essential for a guidance and counseling service by developing students' skills building from planning, implementation, evaluation, and follow-up. Guidance and counseling services are one of the facilities for students directly or indirectly in order to help students to be able to develop their potential or solve problems experienced, both personal issues, family, and peers. Potential development is not only seen in terms of academic potential but can also see from non-academic potential. This article's writing brings by documenting and reviewing all articles related to counseling and skills-building services for students. The steps in this research are analyzing, determining the focus of the topic of scientific work, collecting data from several references and analyzing several literary works relevant to the subject matter, and making conclusions. The articles used in this study were 20 national and international accredited journal articles accessed from google scholar, science direct, and lens.Org. The results of a review of journals and several references found that in the 2013-2020 period, counseling and skills-building services for students held a potential student test next with the Interesting Club activities covering Arabic, English Tahfidzul Qur'an, and Entrepreneurship classes. By forming students who are graceful in character and superior in work.

Keyword : Management, Counseling Guidance Services, and Skills Building

Subject :

[AR-0239]

**IMPLEMENTATION OF MARKETING MIX AND BRAND IMAGE AS
EDUCATIONAL SERVICES MARKETING STRATEGY IN ISLAMIC
EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS**

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UNIVERSITAS MUHAMMADIYAH SIDOARJO

Abstract

This article discusses the marketing strategy of educational services at Islamic educational institutions by applying the marketing mix and brand image. This is motivated by efforts to create quality Islamic educational institutions, so that they are able to compete with other educational institutions. The influence of the globalization of education has a serious impact on the competition in the world of education to be able to produce quality human resources that are reliable and competitive. People as consumers of education have started to look for and choose quality schools, because they are worried that their children will not be able to compete in the current era of globalization. Marketing of educational services is intended to create conducive and stable marketing conditions, so as to have a positive impact on the parties involved in the marketing process, both educational institutions as producers and society as consumers. By applying the marketing mix and brand image as a marketing strategy for educational services, it is expected to increase public interest which will certainly have an impact on increasing the number of students. The method used in this study is a qualitative method by conducting observations and interviews with various parties. Based on the results of research conducted at several Islamic educational institutions, it is proven that the application of the theory of Marketing Mix and Brand Image has an effect on people's beliefs and interests, especially the Muslim community, both with traditional and modern backgrounds which are the marketing segmentation of educational services.

Keyword : Marketing Mix Brand Image Marketing Strategy Education Services

Subject :

[AR-0242]

INTEGRAL EDUCATION BASED ON TAUHID IN FORMING KAMIL PEOPLE

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SD Integral Hidayatullah Probolinggo

Abstract

Islamic education and national education both aim to form intelligent, faithful and pious human beings or students. In practice, we often see a dichotomy, where there is no integration between general science (science) and religious knowledge (deen). From these problems it is necessary to build an integral education model. This study aims to analyze the concept of monotheism-based integral education that is able to lead students, teachers, and the school community to recognize, understand, practice, and enjoy Islam as a real way of life. The method in this study uses a literature study using previous research articles on the lens.org site with a time span of 2017-2021. The results of this study indicate that monotheistic-based integral education is a conscious, structured, and systematic effort to succeed in the mission of human creation based on the guidance of revelation and the results of this monotheistic-based integral education produce insan kamil.

Keyword : integral education, based tauhid

Subject :

[AR-0299]

**Implementation Of Online Blended Learning To Developing
Problem Solving Skill, Learning Motivation And Students
Engagement In Mathematical Physics II Course In Covid-19
Pandemic**

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0269 Ketut Suma)

Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha

Abstract

Abstract. This study aims to identify the impact of applying blended learning on the teaching of Mathematical Physics II (FIS1221) during the COVID-19 pandemic on problem solving skill, learning motivation, and student engagement in the physics education study program at Ganesha University. The study followed a pre-experimental approach. The research subjects consisted of 27 fourth semester students. The pre-test and post-test data on problem-solving ability were taken with a problem-solving test, while the learning motivation data were taken using a questionnaire. Data on learning engagement were only taken in the post-test with a questionnaire. Data analysis was done descriptively, t-test for problem solving ability and learning motivation. Meanwhile, data on learning engagement were analyzed using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test. The results showed that; (1) there is a significant difference in the average score of solving ability between pre-test and post-test, (2) there is a significant difference in the average score of learning motivation between pre-test and post-test, (3) there is a difference in student engagement scores with standard scores specified (passing grade). Blended learning is an effective approach in developing problem-solving skills, learning motivation, and student engagement.

Keyword : Blended Learning, Problem Solving Skill, Learning Motivation, Student Engagement

Subject :

Building Teacher Achievement Motivation During The Covid-19 Pandemic

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

The teacher is the main element that has an essential role in the world of education. Its existence is a determinant of the success of students and the quality of education. This is in line with the goal of the Indonesian state as stated in the 1945 Constitution, namely the intellectual life of the nation. During the Covid-19 pandemic, which lasted from 2019 to 2021, teachers were faced with an uncertain condition, where all educational activities were carried out online without face-to-face interaction. This condition, of course, demands changes in teacher behavior in guiding, training, educating, and teaching students. Not all teachers can adapt to new behaviors and cultures during the Covid-19 pandemic. Many teachers experience a decrease in motivation, even to the point of depression. They are, moreover, faced with the conditions and infrastructure of the internet network where not all teachers and students can access it. This article examines in depth through searching and reviewing various literature to explore how to increase teacher motivation to excel even during the Covid-19 pandemic. From a search of multiple work of literature carried out by the author, it turns out that there are several efforts that educational institutions can take to increase teacher motivation in achieving work performance during the Covid-19 pandemic, including (1) instilling and directing teachers to targets, goals and performance achievement. Clear and measurable, (2) conducting coaching, training, and organizing activities together in a teacher working group or MGMP (Subject Teacher Conference), (3) providing insight into the urgency of developing professional teacher competencies during the Covid-19 pandemic, (4) giving awards to teachers who excel and innovate. Through these efforts, it turned out to be able to increase the achievement motivation of teachers during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Keyword : Achievement motivation, Teacher, COVID-19
Subject :

[AR-0194]

**STRATEGY TO IMPROVE ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE TO
IMPROVE TEACHER PERFORMANCE DURING THE COVID
PANDEMIC**

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Maryono, Karunia Adinda, Daris Sambiono, Tria Wahyuningtyas /
University Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo),*

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0199 TRIA WAHYUNINGTYAS)

Abstract

A strong organizational culture is a force that can unite goals, create motivation, commitment, loyalty, and performance of all school residents, and provide the necessary structure and control without relying on formal bureaucracy. Organizational culture is expected to improve school quality, performance in school and quality of life that is expected to have healthy, dynamic or active, positive and professional characteristics. The goal of the study was to find out how strategies to build organizational culture to improve teacher performance in this pandemic period. This research is conducted using qualitative descriptive research methods. The data sources used in this study are primary data and secondary data with systematic literature review (SLR) techniques carried out in three stages, namely planning, implementation and reporting of the results of literature reviews. The results obtained in this study are expected to provide an overview of how efforts in obtaining organizational cultural strategies to wards improving performance during pandemics.

Keyword : Organizational culture, teacher performance, pandemic
Subject :

[AR-0219]

HUMAN RESOURCES DEVELOPMENT IN THE INDUSTRIAL ERA 4.0 : A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

(AC-1704 Doni Maryono / Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo), (AC-1705 Karunia Adinda / Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo), (AC-1706 Daris Sambiono / Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo), (AC-1707 Tria Wahyuningtyas / Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo), (AC-1708 Sigit Hermawan / Muhammadiyah University of Sidoarjo),

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Muhammadiyah University Of Sidoarjo

Abstract

Organizations are required to continue to make changes in order to continue to grow or at least to survive. The external change that is happening now is the industrial revolution 4.0. The industrial revolution 4.0 has caused disruption. The company's human resource management must develop human resources in the industrial era 4.0. How is the development of human resources in the industrial era 4.0?. The research objective is to answer the research question. The study used a systematic literature reviews method according to the method of Kitchenham and Charters 2007. Based on the research, it is concluded that human resource development plays an important and strategic role in preparing qualified and competent human resources according to the industrial era 4.0. HR development outputs: improving the quality of human resources, leadership, HR competencies mastering technology and data literacy. Alternative strategies for developing human resources for education and training, Continuing Professional Development, skills upgrading or updating programs. The implication is that organizations must develop their human resources by implementing strategies that are in accordance with their organizations so that organizations can survive and have strong competitiveness in industry 4.0

Keyword : Human Resource Development, Industrial Era 4.0, Systematic Literature Review

Subject :

[AR-0256]

**STRATEGY OF MICRO SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES
(MSMEs) DURING COVID-19 AT DELI SERDANG DISTRICT
(AC-1161 Satria Tirtayasa / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara),
(AC-1162 Mohammad Yusri /Universitas Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara),**

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara (UMSU)*

Abstract

Abstract.Indonesia is one of the countries whose economy has been affected by Covid-19. The impact of Covid-19 on the performance of MSMEs is important to study because MSMEs in Indonesia have contributed to National Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of 35%. Therefore, this study aims to make a mapping of the performance of MSME in Deli Serdang Regency and make strategies to increase the competitiveness of MSME in Deli Serdang Regency during Covid-19. The population of this research are the MSME that still survive during the Covid-19 pandemic spread in 3 sub- districts (Pantai Labu Sub-district, Percut Sei District, Tuan and Hamparan Perak Sub-district, which are included in the coastal area in Deli Serdang Regency. The sample in this research is MSME centers that carry out raw material processing, processing, finished materials, and marketing activities (purposive sampling). Sample size uses the Krejcie-Morgan formula with a 90% confidence level, which is 90 MSME businesses . Data analysis using SWOT analysis and research results, namely: Mapping the performance of MSMEs in Deli Serdang Regency is in Quadrant III, which is Defensive Strategy (WT). Furthermore, the implication of this study are follows: MSMEs have to make some strategies to maintain their performance, for instance : Minimize promotions by fostering relationships with customers, Reduced production capacity, Promotion of products online, Purchase of raw materials online, and Cash assistance for working capital.

Keyword : Strategy, MSME, Covid-19, SWOT

Subject :

[AR-0036]

Society Mobility Index Analysis During Transition Period Of Covid-19 Pandemic In East Java

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Abstract

Covid-19 pandemic occurred in Indonesia and also almost all countries in the world has a big impact in various fields, both in health, education, social and economic. The government issued a policy to stay at home to minimize spread of covid-19 virus. In early June 2020 the government issued a new policy, namely New Normal policy. Society mobility indeks of course has changed starting from the stay at home policy until the new normal policy implemented. Google responds to society mobility during the covid 19 pandemic by using navigation technology installed on individual accounts. The aim of visits during pandemic to the transition period is recorded and presented in form of a daily mobility index. This study aims to determine the mobility index of the people of East Java during the transition period of covid 19 pandemic. The results of analysis society mobility index show that the average society mobility index in workplaces has decreased by 20% compared to the baseline period, on the contrary average society mobility index in residential has increased by 12% compared to baseline period. compared to the baseline period. The average society mobility index in transit places, retail and recreation, parks also decreased by 5%, 13% and 32% respectively compared to baseline period. Based on the results of society mobility index analysis, there was a significant change in society mobility index in East Java during transition period compared to baseline period.

Keyword : Society Mobility Index, Covid 19 Pandemic, East Java

Subject :

[AR-0177]

Digital Apps Based On The Flipped Group Discussion Learning Method During The Covid 19 Pandemic

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Abstract

Blended learning is a face-to-face (conventional) learning method combined with e-learning or distance learning methods based on digital technology to complement each other. What has been done so far is after the Covid 19 pandemic. Where online learning and e-learning are carried out due to limited movement between students, teachers and educational institutions which are hindered by the spread of the covid-19 virus. In this study, e-learning was created that supports blended learning during the covid 19 pandemic. Where e-learning was built for teachers, students and parents. The functionality of this e-learning for students is checking students' health during each online learning, choosing learning methods with videos, sounds, modules and assignments as well as online face-to-face learning links. As for teachers, namely uploading assignments, managing subjects, evaluating student assessments, and checking the learning models carried out by students. E-learning is called KelasBalik because it uses a reverse learning model where students before studying in class study the material at home according to the tasks given by the teacher.

Keyword : Flipped Classrom, Blended Learning, Learning Model

Subject :

[AR-0260]

Improving Students' Intelligence With Literacy

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(AC-1581 Benny Prasetya / STAI Muhammadiyah Probolinggo), (AC-1582 Hanafi / MI Muhammadiyah 1 kota Probolinggo),

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

Reading is essential to support the knowledge that students in every academic unit must master. Many factors cause the decline in students' interest in reading, which is influenced by external factors such as the increasing number of types of entertainment and the influence of social media, TV and YouTube in the era of globalization of information and technology as it is today. From the internal side, the ignorance of teachers and parents towards reading and studying habits also makes students lazy. This study uses literature and articles or previous research on literacy in educating students for the 2020-2021 period on the Lens.org, DOAJ.ORG, Scopus, Sinta. The articles used were 18 national and international accredited journal articles. The themes and analysis show changes in the main tools and student habits in literacy to grow students' intelligence. From these problems, there are several solutions and supporting factors, such as the role of the government in making policies and the role of significant collaboration between parents and teachers to increase children's reading interest, which will add broad knowledge and insight.

Keyword : reading, literature, student intelligence

Subject :

[AR-0249]

Principal's Democratic Leadership Style On Teacher Performance
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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

Improving teacher performance is one of the factors of school success. The performance of teachers in schools influences school progress and setbacks. In improving teacher performance, it takes the role of the principal with the leadership style that is played. The democratic leadership style can be used by school principals to improve teacher performance. This study aims to analyze the contribution of the principal's democratic leadership style to teacher performance. The research method uses a literature study using previous research articles on the lens.org site, Google scholar, and science direct. From the results of this study, the democratic leadership style gives its subordinates broad authority. Every time there is a problem, always involve assistants in a complete team to solve the problem. Leaders who use a democratic leadership style provide a lot of information about the duties and responsibilities of their subordinates, and all members are invited to participate or contribute their thoughts and energy to achieve the goals that have been set. Specifically, the principal's democratic leadership style can influence and improve teacher performance.

Keyword : Principal, Democratic leadership, Teacher performance

Subject :

[AR-0203]

**Utilization Of Information And Communication Technology (ICT)
In Developing Islamic Education In The Era Of New Normal
(AC-1474 Rizka Fauziah / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo), (AC-1475
Isa Anshori / Universitas**

**Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo), (AC-1476 Eni Fariyatul Fahyuni / Universitas
Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo),**

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0208 Rizka Fauziah)

Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

This paper examined the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the development of Islamic education in the era of new normal or new habits in the Covid-19 pandemic. This paper describes how ICT is used in administrative management, information systems, communication, and learning processes at Islamic Educational Institutions during the Covid-19 pandemic so that Islamic Education will increasingly exist and develop. This paper used the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method, the references study sourced from Google Scholar, DOAJ, Research Gate, SINTA, Science Direct, and LENS.ORG. The results showed that ICT in Islamic education has a positive impact so that Islamic education becomes more advanced than before. Thus, the Covid-19 pandemic is no longer to be an obstacle. However, it became a trigger for the advancement of Islamic education by utilizing information and communication technology. It showed from the positive response of the people towards Islamic education and current educational policies, which mainly maximizes the use of information and communication technology.

Keyword : information and communication technology, Islamic education, Covid-19 pandemic, new normal

Subject :

[AR-0196]

Can A Green Marketing Strategy Increase Sales Of A Product?
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Sidoarjo), (AC-1454 Sigit Hermawan/ Universitas Muhammadiyah
Sidoarjo),

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

People are increasingly aware of the bad effects of using materials that are not environmentally friendly. Consumers tend to prefer products that are environmentally friendly, so that the presence of green marketing can support increased product sales. On the other hand, environmentally friendly products tend to be more expensive, because the materials used are more expensive. The question arises, can a green marketing strategy increase sales of a product? The purpose of this article is to find out whether green marketing strategies can attract consumers and increase product sales. The method used in this article uses a Systematic Literature Review that uses Lens.org as a literature source. Using how to filter keywords that match the content of the theme of this article. The results show that not all green marketing strategies can increase profits. The green marketing strategy carried out in underdeveloped areas is not very effective. Green marketing strategies can increase sales of a product if it is used in big cities and consumers who are already concerned about the importance of environmentally friendly products.

Keyword : Green Marketing, Sistematic Literature Review, Sales

Subject :

[AR-0180]

**EDUCATION DURING PANDEMIC USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY:
SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW**

(AC-1529 AHMAD RIO DAVID / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo),

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

Since the COVID-19 pandemic hit in the country, educational activities that involve all parties in the learning process are required to be able to use facilities and various applications that can facilitate the learning process, therefore the use and optimization of digital technology media is a priority. The benefits and objectives of using digital technology media optimally are so that educators and students can communicate well and work well together so that they can make changes in today's modern world of technology. The method used in this study is Systematic Literature Review so that it is able to identify, review, evaluate, and interpret all forms of research with interesting phenomena themes, and of course also relevant research questions. The implementation of education in the Covid 19 pandemic era requires all parties involved in the learning process to be skilled in using facilities and various platforms that can facilitate all learning activities, for that the urgency of using digital literacy during education during this pandemic is a top priority. The goal of mastering the use of digital literacy is expected that both educators and students or students are able to actively participate and be involved in providing a change that is sensitive to technology that is currently developing. The method used is the Systematic Literature Review in order to be able to identify, study, evaluate, and interpret all available research with topic areas of interesting phenomena, with certain relevant research questions.

Keyword : Media Technology Digital, Digital Literacy, Pandemic Covid19

Subject :

[AR-0221]

**Systematic Literature Review: The Tajdied Method To Improve
Studentsâ€™ Ability To Read The Qur'an**
*(AC-1520 Teguh Abdillah / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo), (AC-1521
Taufik Churrahman / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo),*

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0215 Teguh Abdillah)

SD Muhammadiyah 1 Driyorejo

As an Islamic educational institution concerned with Islamic education, the application of Al-Qur'an learning should be a special program. But in reality, there are still many complaints from parents about the ability to read the Qur'an in their children. Meanwhile, teaching the Qur'an is an obligation for every Muslim based on Al-Hadith; the best of you are those who learn and teach the Qur'an. The problem here is whether the application of Al-Qur'an learning so far has been relevant to producing good reading skills. Based on this, the author tries to apply the Qur'anic learning method that optimizes intelligence, visual, auditory, and kinesthetic, by using the Tajdied method of learning the Qur'an. The purpose of this study was to improve learning outcomes and the ability to read the Qur'an for elementary school students. The method used in this study is a descriptive qualitative method with the type of Classroom Action Research. The results of this study indicate that the application of learning the Qur'an using the Tajdied method affects increasing the ability to read the Qur'an of elementary school students.

Keyword : Tajdied method, students ability to read the Quran

Subject :

[AR-0195]

**Implementation Of Islamic School Culture In The Formation Of
Religious Character Of Students In The Covid-19 Pandemic
(AC-1455 Rusiati / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo), (AC-1456 Biyanto
/ UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya), (AC-1457 Eni Fariatul Fahyuni / Universitas
Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo),**

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0202 RUSIATI)

UNIVERSITAS MUHAMMADIYAH SIDOARJO

Abstract

Growing and developing the potential of students to become human beings who believe in and are faithful to God is the educational goal of every school. To that end, the school applies Islamic school culture for habituation in schools. Islamic school culture includes smiles, greetings and shaking hands, tolerance, dhuha praying, reading holly Qur'an, learning religious talks, praying dhuhr, praying together. This Islamic school culture is carried out by all school residents while in school. The purpose of this Islamic school culture is to form the religious character of all school residents. The Covid-19 pandemic made Islamic school culture impossible because students had to study at home or school but with reduced study time. Communication between parents and schools is more intensive in monitoring student activities during home study. Researchers examined previous research to understand the obstacles and solutions in applying Islamic school culture and the religious character of learners during the Covid-19 pandemic. This research was conducted in the Systematic Literature Review by documenting and reviewing Islamic school culture, spiritual feeling, and the Covid-19.pandemic in 2017-2021. The number of pieces taken amounted to 18 articles from national and international journals accessed from DOAJ, Google Scholar. The study results revealed that good communication between teachers and parents of students can help the habituation of Islamic school culture learners in forming religious character that is usually done in school but now done in their respective homes.

Keyword : Islamic school culture, Religious character, Covid-19

Subject :

[AR-0206]

Strategies For Increasing The Quality Outcome Of Educational Outcomes At The Elementary School Level

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0218 Anik Wakhidah)

SD Muhammadiyah 2 Kejapanan

The results of an educational process can be in the form of outputs that are realized in the form of how many students graduate at an educational institution and can also be in the form of outcomes that are realized in the form of how the quality or quality of learning outcomes is felt by the user institution. User institutions that mostly feel the quality of student outcomes at Elementary Schools (SD)/Madrasah Ibtidaiyah (MI) are on average Junior High Schools (SMP)/Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs). The quality of student outcomes at the elementary school level must always be evaluated in a planned, systematic, periodic, and sustainable manner so that from time to time it can be improved. The quality of student outcomes that are not evaluated will never be able to measure the level of success indicators, which include the value of effectiveness, efficiency and productivity. In order to improve the quality of outcomes or student outcomes at the SD/MI level, an appropriate, proportional and professional strategy is needed to make it happen. This article tries to examine how strategies to improve the quality of student outcomes at the elementary school level. An indepth study was carried out by tracing some of the relevant literature. From the search results on various literatures, it is found that there are several strategies to improve the quality of student outcomes at the elementary school level, including: (1) increasing the competence of teachers and education personnel, (2) improving administrative, academic, counseling and internet-based information services (online).) especially in the Covid'19 pandemic era, (3) selective, effective, efficient and attractive use and utilization of educational media, (4) involving user institutions (users) and related elements to provide feedback on the quality of student outcomes. . Through the implementation of some of these strategies, the quality of student outcomes is expected to be improved in a better and more advanced direction.

Keyword : strategy, quality improvement, student outcomes, elementary school

Subject :

[AR-0215]

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE PRINCIPAL

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0228 Mariza Hadul Aslamiyah)

University Of Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

The principal's leadership in an organization or institution has a reasonably heavy task and responsibility; therefore, a leader must have the ability in all fields in management, stakeholders, socializing, and motivating to improve superior and quality school results. An accomplished school certainly has a headteacher who is directly involved. The principal's leadership style factor is a supporting factor and the key to a successful or outstanding school. However, not a few of the principals experience difficulties, obstacles, and even setbacks in their institutions and adversely affect the school to affect the quality and accreditation of the school. Some of the results of previous research have explained the relationship between the principal's leadership style and the improvement of the external quality assurance system is very close to realizing a superior and outstanding school. To overcome the problem has been carried out a systematic literature review by documenting and reviewing all articles related to the leadership style of the principal and external quality assurance system. Researchers searched for data using journal articles in JAMP, Lens.org, Google Scholar, Academia. There were 25 articles between 2019-2021. The results show that the failure and success of an institution are primarily determined by the leader in playing its role, so a democratic, innovative, effective, and dynamic leadership style can increase the external quality assurance system.

Keyword : leadership style, headmaster, external quality assurance system.

Subject :

[AR-0220]

Headmaster's Leadership In Islamic Educational Institutions During The COVID-19 Pandemic

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0230 Arum Ndalul)

SD Muhammadiyah 1 Krian

Abstract

One of the factors affecting quality Islamic education institutions is the Principal's leadership, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. The unpreparedness of teachers in learning becomes a significant obstacle because of changes in the teacher teaching system that must be digital-based, and all components of the school are required to maintain stable body conditions. In contrast, the Principal is required to think that the learning process continues to run smoothly. As a result, many components of the school feel the burden of work and performance decreases. This article aims for all school members to keep the spirit of improving their performance during the COVID-19 pandemic. The method used is a Systematic Literature Review set against the background of the COVID-19 pandemic situation that is still ongoing to provide obstacles for writers to jump in the field. The writing of this article is carried out by documenting and reviewing all articles related to the Principal's leadership in Islamic educational institutions during the COVID-19 pandemic period 2019-2021. The first step is to analyze, determine the focus of the article's topic, then collect data from some literature and conduct an analysis of content relevant to the issue of discussion, then provide conclusions. The reports used in the study were 20 nationally and internationally accredited journal articles accessed from google scholar, SINTA, Science direct, and lens.Org and then corroborated by the source of 2 books

Keyword : Principal leadership, Islamic Education, COVID-19 pandemic.

Subject :

[AR-0232]

The Online Counselling Guidance For Indonesian Millennial Students

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

This study aims to identify that students urgently online counselling guidance Indonesian millennial students during the COVID-19 pandemic. The online counselling guidance improves self-efficacy and achievement motivation in educational conditions limited by distance, space and time. The research method uses quantitative and qualitative approaches to identify the dominant variables of online counselling guidance, self-efficacy and student achievement motivation. The findings of this study have implications for millennial era online counselling services that emphasize three factors; students have skills, develop learning strategies, students' internal and external motivation. For this reason, educators or counsellors must help find ways and approaches to improve student learning readiness according to the potential and skills possessed by each individual.

Keyword : online counselling guidance, self-efficacy, achievement motivation

Subject :

[AR-0175]

Solar Panel Energy Learning In Junior High School
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Mahmud Efendy / Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang),

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0166 Yus Mochamad Cholily)
Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang

Abstract

This paper shows that solar panel energy can and should be taught at the junior high school level. Renewable energy from solar cells can be used as local content material in extra-curricular subjects. The FGD with junior high school teachers in Malang Raya was initiated to incorporate solar cell energy into the Crafts subject. In general, teachers do not know well about solar cells, but teachers realize that energy from the sun is important for the future and needs to be taught in schools. Students' understanding of solar cell energy can be a provision for the future in order to prepare life skills.

Keyword : Solar panel, energy, learning, Junior High School

Subject :

[AR-0090]

I **Want To Ride My Bicycle: Determining Factors Affecting
Intention To Bike Within Greater Jakarta**
*(AC-0824 Bambang Utoyo / MoCE Indonesia), (AC-0825 Izmir Azlan / MCIT
Indonesia), (AC-0826 Nur Hidayat Suroso / MoRA Indonesia), (AC-0827 Arif
Widodo Nugroho / Universitas Muhammadiyah Prof.*

*Dr. HAMKA), (AC-0828 Muhammad Suyuthi Romdlon / Universitas Negeri
Jakarta),*

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0055 Iswahyudi)

Universitas Terbuka

Abstract

In this current pandemic situation, people got a new disease called acute boredom quarantine syndrome. They have been trying to find new activities, one of them is cycling. Cycling gives people double pleasure: it escapes from boredom and makes healthy at the same time. This interesting phenomenon is rising in the Greater Jakarta area. Intention to bike was determined by several factors that were decomposed from the Theory of planned behavior (TPB) and Flow theory. However, there are limited studies on Flow theory on the biking trends context within Indonesia. To address this gap, this study aims to examine the determinants affecting intention to bike on daily cyclists. Using the data collected from all cyclists who bike regularly in the Greater Jakarta area, we conducted a structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis. Our study may contribute to advancing our knowledge of how habit, perceived enjoyment, perceived peer influence, serious leisure, flow state, attitude towards biking are related, and how these relationships affect the intention to bike. The findings of this study provide several important implications for biking activists and governments alike to create sustainable policies in the future.

Keyword : intention to bike, TPB, flow, biking trends

Subject : Psychology

[AR-0095]

UTILIZATION OF DIGITAL MARKETING FOR MICRO, SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES

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Muhammadiyah Prof DR HAMKA),

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0109 Edi Setiawan)

Universitas Muhammadiyah Prof DR HAMKA

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the implementation of the use of digital marketing for MSME entrepreneurs in Jakarta. This research method uses a quantitative approach using descriptive analytical methods. The sampling technique was carried out randomly with a total of 200 MSMEs taken and fulfilled the criteria of 112 MSMEs. The results showed that simultaneously sales and awareness variables significantly influence the understanding of digital marketing variables.

Keyword : Quantitative, utilization, sales, awareness

Subject :

[AR-0151]

The Local Fairy Tales For Teaching Writing
(AC-0843 Wahyu Taufiq / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo),

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0152 Wahyu Taufiq)
Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

The study investigated the use of local fairy tales in teaching writing, particularly in narrative text during pandemic covid19 in TEFL Context. This research used a pre-experimental design using a class of ten grade students of a high school in East Java Indonesia. The results show that the pre-test is 50.33 and post-test is 74.66 which means that there is an improvement after the students got treatment. The N-Gain score is 0.468 and it includes "average criteria". It indicates that by using the local fairy tales in the form of short videos as media can improve students' writing skill of narrative text.

Keyword : Fairy tales, Media, Writing Skill, Narrative Text

Subject : Education

[AR-0073]

Potential Of Essential Oils Of Cananga Flowers (Cananga Odorata) As Antibacterials In Hand Sanitizer Gel Preparations (AC-0434 Eka Herlina / Chemistry Departement, FMIPA Universitas Pakuan), (AC-0435 Diana Widiastuti/ Chemistry Departement, FMIPA Universitas Pakuan), (AC-0436 Akhwan Triadi / Chemistry Departement, FMIPA Universitas Pakuan),

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0099 Eka Herlina)

Universitas Pakuan

Abstract

The natural resources are increasingly being used as a medicine for both pharmaceuticals and agricultural purposes in Indonesia recently. One of these resources is cananga plants which can be used as essential oils as antibacterial ingredients for hand sanitizer products. The essential oil is obtained through distillation process, and its phytochemical identification is tested, including specific gravity, refractive index, and ester numbers according to SNI 06-3949-1995. Finally, its potential for antibacterial activity is also tested. The hand sanitizer gel with essential oil of cananga flower was made in 4 formulas; each with the concentration of essential oils of cananga flower was 5%; 2,5%; 1,25% and 0,5%. The obtained data includes physical product, viscosity, pH, dispersion, adhesion, organoleptic and antibacterial activity tests. The results showed that a hand sanitizer gel with cananga flower essential oils had antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* bacteria. From the organoleptic test, it was concluded that the hand sanitizer gel with the concentration of 5% essential oils of cananga flower is the most optimum with a pH of 5.75; viscosity of 4120; spread of 5.5 cm² and adhesion power of 18.33 seconds.

Keyword : Essential oil, cananga flower, antibacterial, hand sanitizer gel

Subject : Pharmaceutical Sciences

[AR-0011]

Optimization Model Of Marine Culture In Tuban District

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0018 Marita Ika Joesidawati)

Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe

Abstract

Marine culture is one form of an effort to increase fishery production, in addition to capture fisheries. The waters north of Java, Tuban Regency are developing marine culture using floating net cages with the main commodities of grouper fish and shellfish. The current problem is the limited supporting industries that meet the needs of seeds, fish feed and marine cultivation equipment. In addition, the availability of land is limited because it requires quality waters that are clean and free of pollution. Marine culture development requires government policies to encourage the emergence of supporting industries. As a large investment, a supporting industry can only be created if the marine culture industry is proven to have high economic value. Thus, it is necessary to develop a marine culture model to identify (1) the size of the industry based on available marine resources (land area and water conditions) and (2) to develop an optimization model with linear programming. The result of this research is a linear programming model and the optimal value of each cultivation commodity. Cultivation commodities consist of grouper and shellfish..

Keyword : linier programing, high economic value, supporting industries

Subject :

[AR-0078]

The Effectiveness Of Online Learning Methods On Student Satisfaction During The Pandemic

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0067 Asty Khairi Inayah)

IPB University

Abstract

The first quarter of 2020 has been a difficult time for the global community. The Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic that has hit the world is affecting various sectors, one of which is education. The physical distancing policy makes learning carried out remotely. This study aims to determine the effectiveness of online learning on student satisfaction. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to students using purposes sampling. Data analysis using SEMPLS method. The results showed that students still experienced infrastructure problems in online learning. Lecturer creativity in delivering material is needed. The delivery of material using the lecture method has not been effective considering that the infrastructure owned by students is still lacking. Lecturers are not required to make new applications in the implementation of online learning. However, lecturers can use one or more applications to make the delivery of material to students more interesting and varied in online learning.

Keyword : Online learning, performance of lecture, quality, satisfaction

Subject :

[AR-0122]

Early Detection Of Javanese Phonological Awareness Of Grade 4 Elementary School Students In PJJ

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0139 Endang Sri Maruti)

Universitas Negeri Surabaya

Abstract

This study seeks to detect the phonological awareness of Javanese in elementary school grade 4 students early through the distance learning process. One of the Javanese language materials taught in grade 4 SD is aksara jejeg and aksara miring, both in terms of writing and pronunciation. To be able to determine the level of awareness of children's phonology, one indicator is to look at the child's ability to write and read Javanese text. This research is a descriptive qualitative type. Data was collected by archiving all assignments related to writing and reading Javanese Latin text sent by students through the WhatsApp application in the form of photos of writing assignments and voicenotes when reading text. The collected data were then analyzed descriptively. The results showed that grade 4 elementary school students made many phonological errors when writing and reading Javanese text. The most common mistakes are when writing vowels /a/ and reading consonants /dh/ and /th/. Based on the many errors, it can be concluded that the phonological awareness of Javanese elementary school students in grade 4 is still low, or it can be said to be less aware.

Keyword : Javanese phonological awareness, aksara jejeg, aksara miring

Subject : Arts and Humanities

[AR-0017]

Overconfidence And Cognitive Dissonance Behavior In The Pension Fund Investment Manager In The New Normal Era (AC-0877 Sri Utami Ady / Universitas Dr. Soetomo), (AC-0878 Alvy Mulyaning Tyas / Universitas Dr. Soetomo), (AC-0879 Ilya Farida / Universitas Dr. Soetomo), (AC-0880 Aries Widya Gunawan / Universitas Airlangga),

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0024 Sri Utami Ady)

Universitas Dr. Soetomo

Abstract

This study aimed to explore overconfidence and cognitive dissonance behavior in the Pension Fund Investment Manager, both DPPK (Dana Pensiun Pemberi Kerja) and DPLK (Dana Pensiun Lembaga Keuangan) in the New This study aimed to explore overconfidence and cognitive dissonance behavior in the Pension Fund Investment Manager, both DPPK (Dana Pensiun Pemberi Kerja) and DPLK (Dana Pensiun Lembaga Keuangan) in the New Normal era after Covid-19 Pandemic. Used the qualitative phenomenological method, data collection carried out by in-depth interviews with six informants who were representatives of 3 pension funds, followed by observation and documentation. The results indicated that from a prudent perspective, DPPK was more conservative than DPLK, for safety considerations, tight control from superiors, and least fund, make the Investment Manager almost malfunction properly. Unlike the DPLK, which has a larger fund, innovating in investment management was more significant. They tend given the freedom to be responsible for managing investment funds, although they still didn't violate the corridors and rules of the OJK. These results showed both types of pension funds; the DPLK has a higher return than the DPPK.

Keyword : pension fund, overconfidence; cognitive dissonance; qualitative

Subject : Finance

[AR-0048]

**Analysis Of The Effect Of Pentagon Fraud In Detecting Fraud
Financial Statement Using The F-Score Method (Empirical Study
Of Manufacturers Listed On The Indonesia Stock Exchange 2015-
2019 Period)**

(AC-0554 Vina Yusniarti /), (AC-0555 Henny Mulyati /), (AC-0556 Amrizal),

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0063 Vina Yusniarti, S.Ak)

ITB Ahmad Dahlan Socio Technopreneur University

Abstract

This study aims to examine the elements of fraud in the fraud pentagon theory in detecting financial statement fraud. Pentagon fraud is variables from the pressure element, opportunity, rationalization, capability, and elements of arrogance, namely political relationships which are hypothesized to affect financial statement fraud. The F-Score method is used to determine financial statement fraud. This research sample was selected using the purposive sampling method from 47 manufacturing companies in the basic industry and chemicals industry listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) in the period 2015 to 2019. Hypothesis testing uses multiple regression analysis models using SPSS 22 to test the effect of the target. finance, financial stability, external pressure, institutional share ownership, ineffective supervision, influence on the nature of the industry, quality of external auditors, replacement of auditors, change of directors and political relations to financial statement fraud. The results showed that the quality of external auditors and auditor turnover had a significant positive effect on financial statement fraud. Meanwhile, financial targets, financial stability, external pressure, institutional share ownership, ineffective supervision, the influence of the nature of the industry, the change of directors, and political relations have no effect on financial statement fraud.

Keyword : Finance and Banking, Financial Statement Fraud, Pentagon Fraud, f-Score model

Subject : Finance and Banking

[AR-0075]

Weather Forecast Using Learning Vector Quantization Methods *(AC-0809 Siska Andriani /), (AC-0810 Kotim Subandi /),*

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0100 Siska Andriani)

Universitas Pakuan

Abstract

Weather forecasting is one of the important factors in daily life, as it can affect the activities carried out by the community. The study was conducted to optimize weather forecasts using artificial neural network methods. The artificial neural network used is a learning vector quantization (LVQ) method, in which artificial neural networks based on previous research are suitable for prediction. The research is modeling weather forecast optimization using the LVQ method. Models with the best accuracy can be used in terms of weather forecasts. Based on the results of the training that has been done in this study produces the best accuracy on the LVQ method which is to produce 71%.

Keyword : optimization, weather forecast, learning vector quantization.

Subject : Science

[AR-0070]

Buying Interests, Attitudes And Maqosid Sharia

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0094 Zulpahmi)

Universitas Muhammadiyah Prof. Dr. HAMKA

Abstract

This research aims to determine the analysis of samyang buying interest factors through attitude as intervening based on maqosid sharia. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires. The method used quantitative with purposive sampling technique. This analysis includes validity, reliability, classic assumption and statistical tests using path analysis. The results showed that the variable knowledge of products and prices have a positive and significant effect on attitude. Whereas halal certification and halal awareness do not affect attitudes. Furthermore, the price and attitude had a positive and significant effect on buying interest. Whereas product knowledge, halal certification and halal awareness do not affect buying interest. Attitude variables can mediate product knowledge and prices towards samyang buying interest. In addition, the results of the hypothesis using the F-test showed that the variables of product knowledge, halal certification, halal awareness, price, and attitude simultaneously (together) had a positive effect on buying interest.

Keyword : Maqosid Sharia, Product Knowledge, Halal Certification, Halal Awareness, Price, Attitude and

Subject :

[AR-0066]

**The Implementation Of New Normal Online Schools For The
Elementary School In Indonesia
(AC-0393 VEY LIANSARI / UNIVERSITAS MUHAMMADIYAH SIDOARJO),**

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0088 VEY LIANSARI)

UNIVERSITAS MUHAMMADIYAH SIDOARJO

Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic happened in Indonesia since March 2020. It made all activities that gather large numbers of people to be avoided. Therefore, the activities teaching and learning process usually in the classroom. Nowadays, it changes into online learning during the new normal period. The function of online learning in the new normal period is to connect educators and students through the internet network that could be accessed anytime and anywhere. There are many kinds of online media when online learning such as the WhatsApp group, Google Classroom, Website, and other online media. The purpose of this study is to know the implementation of online schools in the new normal period for almost 6 months in the elementary school of Indonesia. The method used collecting sample data in the form of questions and answers to teachers, students, and parents of elementary school students regarding the results that have been felt during online school for elementary school students. The results of this study, it can be concluded that collaboration between teachers, students, and parents is very important. Thus, online schools can run based on their goals and expected outcomes. In addition, the basic abilities of each competency will not be achieved properly, this is because there are several factors that become obstacles including the existence of material that requires face-to-face contact with students, honesty between students and parents of students for assignments given by the teacher, signals that substandard, insufficient technology, as well as children's psychological factors. Children will get bored when learning is done online continuously, therefore it is important to do it in collaboration between 50% online and 50% offline.

Keyword : effectiveness, online, learning, new normal

Subject :

[AR-0025]

The Anemia And Incidence Prolonged Second Stage Of Labor
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Stikes Karya Husada Kediri

Abstract

The prevalence of anemia in pregnant women in Indonesia was 48.9% in 2018. Long labor is the most common complication experienced by pregnant women who are anaemi which is a total of 41%. The objective of this study is to find out the relationship of anemia with the incidence of Second Stage Prolonged. Design analytical research with a case control approach. The data is searched retrospectively. Independent variables of anemia and dependent variables of the incidence of Second Stage Prolonged. The research was conducted at Dr. Iskak Tulungagung Hospital. The population was 2,379 with a sample size of 164 respondents taken with Simple Random Sampling. Analyze data using spearman rank test. There is a relationship between anemia and the incidence of elongated kala II ($p=0.000 < 0.05$), $r = 0.524$. OR shows a figure of 9.9, meaning anemia is at risk of more than 9.9 times experiencing incidence of Second Stage Prolonged compared to those that are not anaemi. The lower the haemoglobin level the higher the lengthened Second Stage, the less oxygen in the blood causes the uterine muscles to be unable to contract strongly which triggers the onion of the incidence of Second Stage Prolonged Keywords : anemia, Second Stage Prolonged, labor

Keyword : anemia, Second Stage Prolonged, labor

Subject :

[AR-0027]

Lusi Island Tourism Development In Sidoarjo During New Normal Era Using Collaborative Governance Approach
(AC-0098 Isnaini Rodiyah / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo), (AC-0099 Hendra Sukmana /

Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo), (AC-0100 Monicha Puspitasari / Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo),

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0035 Isnaini Rodiyah)

Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

The purpose of this research are to analyze and describe 1) The impact of Covid 19 pandemic in the development of Lusi Island tourism in Sidoarjo; 2) Development of Lusi Island tourism in Sidoarjo during new normal period using collaborative governance approach. This research is a qualitative descriptive using purposive sampling technique in determining informants. The data collection technique was done by interview, observation, and documentation. The data analysis used an interactive analysis model proposed by Miles and Huberman, consisting of four components, those are data collection, data reduction, data presentation and draw the conclusion. The results of the research showed that, firstly, the impact of the Covid 19 pandemic on Lusi Island tourism, that is the economic activities of Kedungpandan residents experiencing paralysis because Lusi Island was closed. The officers of Lusi Island tourism have switched professions become fisherman, but catches were less in demand, due to the market opening hours are restricted according to PSBB development policy. The health conditions of Kedungpandan residents who were exposed to Covid 19 there are 4 people under surveillance (ODP) and 4 other people who become patients under surveillance (PDP) (Dinkes Sidoarjo, July 2020). The existing facilities and infrastructure conditions in Lusi Island and Tlocor quay before and after the pandemic were inadequate. Especially during new normal era, it is necessary to do socialization in order to grow awareness and form a behaviour and culture of clean and healthy living, it is also necessary to support facilities and equipment for protecting oneself against various viruses according to health protocols. Secondly, collaborative governance in the development of Lusi Island tourism in the new normal post-Covid-19 pandemic, that is the presence of the Regional Government, Village Government and the private sector has not been seen to revive Lusi Island tourism in order to prepare for New Normal-style tourist visits. In dimension 1) the initial condition that there are different strengths among the actors in the collaboration process; 2) Facilitative leadership is carried out not by the government as a

figure but by POKDARWIS; 3) The institutional design has no legal basis, either in the form of an MOU or other agreement between the Youth, Sports & Tourism Service, Marine & Fisheries Service, Health Service, Kedungpandan Village Government, community (Pokdarwis), APPWS, academicians and the media. Primarily, the presence of the health office is to educate on clean and healthy living in the New Normal era; 4) The collaboration process is only carried out between POKDARWIS and APPWS in online communication (via WhatsApp, telephone), while there has not been communication and coordination with the village government. However, the community (POKDARWIS & APPWS) is committed to reviving Lusi Island as a healthy and safe tourist destination; 5) Outcome, collaboration with no agreement from stakeholders in making decisions to revive and reopen tourism in the New Normal era; 6) The impact of collaboration has not been seen because there is no government or private support for the development of Lusi Island as a safe, comfortable tourist destination and a guarantee that the island is Covid 19 free. Collaboration only occurs between POKDARWIS and APPWS. The collaboration process becomes stronger if the government is present as Actors and driving figures.

Keyword : Collaborative Governance, Stakeholder, Lusi Island Tourism, New Normal Era

Subject :

[AR-0023]

Tongling Performing Arts As The Identity Of The Wonomulyo Village-Genilangit, Indonesia

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

The Wonomulyo village is one of the most potential in the Genilangit village of any other village. As an act of gratitude for the people of the Wonomulyo village - Genilangit of the vast natural resources of this village, so in 1994 one of the Wonomulyo community decided to create an art musical using bamboo Musical Instruments The art of the Tongling performance stands for both Kentongan and Suling (flute), which are important instruments of the Tongling show. Not a part of the ritual, but merely an amusement for the Wonomulyo village folk during special days, such as the harvest, the feasting, the welcome, and so on. Tongling performance art is the only indigenous art of the Wonomulyo village performance, and it is the trademark, identity, and pride of citizens that to this day have grown with the age, without dismissing the true identity of these performance instruments.

Keyword : Tongling performing arts, Wonomulyo, Genilangit
Subject : Arts and Humanities

[AR-0071]

**The Influence Of Product Innovation, Digital Marketing And
Competitive Advantage In Improving The Marketing Performance
Of Small And Medium Industries In Bali.**
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University Of Hindu Indonesia*

Abstract

Digital marketing is currently the most effective marketing model when there is a less contact economy in the Covid-19 pandemic situation. This study focuses on the Small and Medium Industry (IKM) segment as one of the drivers of economic activity in Bali. This study aims to investigate the role of digital marketing in strengthening the relationship of product innovation to marketing performance through competitive advantage. The data were obtained using a survey approach to 196 IKM management respondents throughout Bali. The research hypothesis was tested using structural equation modeling with the help of SmartPLS 3.0 software. The main finding is that all hypotheses can be tested for truth, that there is a direct influence relationship between product innovation and competitive advantage, but when through competitive advantage there is a partial mediation relationship with SMI marketing performance, then digital marketing is able to strengthen the relationship of product innovation in improving SMI marketing performance in Bali. In order for the relationship to product innovation to be real and stronger in marketing performance, the role of competitive advantage and digital marketing is important.

Keyword : Digital marketing, product innovation, competitive advantage,
marketing performance

Subject : Management

[AR-0056]

Challenges Of Sharia Banking Notaries In Indonesia
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Walisongo State Islamic University

Abstract

Notaries have a strategic position in making Islamic banking contracts. The reason is that the notary is responsible for the correctness of the contract construction to fulfill the terms of the agreement and the sharia principles. This study aims to find the philosophy of juridical consequences of the notary profession relationship with Islamic banking, which is associated with challenges in the global era. This research uses a philosophical, juridical, and empirical approach. The analysis results show that a notary who has sharia competence and understands and also carries out the philosophy of juridical consequences of the profession is very much needed. This is due to the growing challenges in developing Islamic banking globally, particularly about competition due to advances in information technology.

Keyword : opportunities, notaries, Islamic banking, Indonesia, global era.

Subject :

[AR-0068]

Tourism Village And Impact On Labor Absorption In Jombang Regency

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University Of Wijaya Putra*

Abstract

The motivation for this research is the success of a program that has been implemented by South Korea, known as Samuel Undong. The purpose of this research is to analyze the impact of the tourism village which consists of tourism objects, souvenir trading business, hotel and lodging business, food stalls and restaurants, transportation business on the absorption of labor in Jombang Regency. The analytical method used is path analysis. The results of the research on tourism object business, souvenir trading business, hotel and lodging business, food stall and restaurant business, transportation business have an effect on employment but not significantly. This means that the potential in the form of a tourist village has not made a significant contribution to employment. This is also proven by the fact that the majority of the workforce who works in the tourism business and its supporting businesses are permanent.

Keyword : Tourism Village, Path Analysis, Tourism Business, Labor Absorption
Subject :

[AR-0046]

**RELATIONSHIP OF PARTICIPATIVE PLANNING, PLANNING
ALIGNMENT AND REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT PERFORMANCE:
EVIDENCE FROM SPECIAL REGION OF YOGYAKARTA
(AC-0863 Andilo Tohom / IPB University), (AC-0864 Ernan Rustiadi / IPB
University), (AC-0865 Bambang**

Juanda / IPB University), (AC-0866 Rilus Kinseng / IPB University),

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IPB University

Abstract

Participatory planning is a necessity. Unfortunately, participatory planning has various problems that make it ineffective. Human resource capacity as an input factor for participatory planning is still inadequate. The participatory planning process has not optimized best ways of producing the outputs that are needed by the community. Spatial aspects of planning, activities in the space, and budgeting must be aligned. However, empirical facts show the inconsistency of development planning. The purpose of this study is to analyze the relationship between community participation in planning and regional development performance through the mediation of variable of spatial planning, development, and budget planning alignment. This study explore measurement of all three variables using quantitative indicators. The results of this study, using SEM PLS, indicate that the direct relationship of community participation and the performance of infrastructure development is significant if it does not include the mediation variable of the planning alignment. Process, results of participatory planning, alignment of spatial and development plans, and alignment of strategic plans with work plans are significant variables. Therefore, local governments need to make efforts to improve participation processes in spatial planning and development so as to improve the regional development planning alignment and performance.

Keyword : development performance, mediating, planning alignment, public participation

Subject : Management

[AR-0040]

DEVELOPMENT OF 500-KV XLPE UNDERGROUND CABLE IN CAPITAL CITY FOR SUSTAINABILITY OF ELECTRIC ENERGY FOR COMMUNITY

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University Of Indonesia

Abstract

Design of 500kV UGC transmission is never been applied in Indonesia. Even around the world, 500 kV UGC designs are still limited. PLN have Jakarta Looping transmission project 500kV. This project has potential delays due to land problems and social constraints along the route. Given that Jakarta is a capital city with very high population, construction of tower transmission will be a special challenge to complete the project, where the process of land acquisition and compensation costs along the route will be special. This research estimate the construction cost for 500 kV UGC as alternative to the project in the urban area. The length will be separate into 4 categories of the OHL route 1)a half of the OHL, 2)same with the OHL, 3) 1.5 times of OHL, and last 4) 2 times of OHL. From the estimated calculations with 4 categories, it is obtained, ratio of construction costs with UGC designs to the OHL design construction costs is smaller than the cost of ratio for the same design in Europe and America. Itâ€™s feasible to execute in urban area.

Keyword : Overhead line; Underground cable; 500 kV; Construction Cost; Ratio

Subject : Electrical Engineering

[AR-0034]

Adjustment Of Antidiabetic Doses Based On Creatinine Clearance And Its Relation With Glycemic Control In Type 2 DM Patients With Chronic Kidney Disease

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0042 EMY OKTAVIANI)

Pharmacy, Pakuan University

Abstract

Adjustment of dose based on creatinine clearance is one of the right steps in adjusting the dose in diabetes patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). The aim of this study was to examine dose adjustments based on creatinine clearance and its relation to glycemic control in type 2 DM with CKD at Fatmawati General Hospital, Indonesia. A cross sectional design with Giusti Hayton's approach was used in this study. From 172 medical records, there were 78 cases (45.35%) with inappropriate doses and based on statistical analysis using Chi Square, it was seen that dose suitability was related to glycemic control in the form of fasting blood glucose ($p = 0.041$) and had no relation to blood glucose 2 hours post prandial ($p = 0.104$).

Keyword : Dose adjustment, creatinine clearance, glycemic control, antidiabetic

Subject : Pharmaceutical Sciences

[AR-0037]

The Feasibility Of Developing Learning Devices Science Concept Based On Android For College Students In Elementary Teaching Program.

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Ronggolawe Tuban), (AC-0861 Muarifatul Munawaroh / Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe Tuban),

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Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe Tuban

Abstract

This research is motivated by efforts to improve scientific literacy skills and build the skills of 21st century students by developing the concept of Android-based science learning devices. Learning device are developed so that students can learn independently, quickly, practically, not limited by time and space, and students are ready to compete in the global world. This study aims to describe the feasibility of developing Android-based science learning tools for PGSD students. This device was developed with a 4-D model by Thiagarajan. The tools developed are: RPP, e-book, LKM and evaluation tools. The research subjects were PGSD UNIROW students who took the Science Concept 2018/2019 course. Collecting data using questionnaires and observations, then analyzed using descriptive statistical analysis techniques. From the results of the validation and test results, it can be concluded that the learning tools developed are categorized as good, valid and suitable for use in learning.

Keyword : feasibility, development, learning device, science concepts, android

Subject : Education

[AR-0100]

FACTORS AFFECTING THE DECISION OF BUYING AT THE CENTRAL CULINARY TOURISM

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0017 Mei Indrawati)

Universitas Wijaya Putra

Abstract

The proliferation of culinary tourism in various regions has caused intense competition. It is important for culinary tourism actors to know the factors that influence someone to purchase their products. The research objective is to analyze the effect of product, price, and word of mouth partially or simultaneously on purchasing decisions at the Culinary Tourism Center. The independent variables include: product, price, and word of mouth. Purchase decision as the dependent variable. A sample of 60 buyers by purposive sampling. Data analysis using Multiple Linear Regression. The regression coefficient of the three independent variables has a significance of less than 0.05, meaning that it partially influences the buying decision. The significance of the F test = 0.000, meaning that it simultaneously influences the buying decision. The research implication makes culinary business players survive.

Keyword : product, price, word of mouth, buying decision, culinary tourism,

Subject : Management

[AR-0055]

English Language Training For Local Community In The Tourism Site Of Karang Talun Mangrove Forest, Cilacap, Central Java
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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0066 Betti Widianingsih)

Politeknik Negeri Cilacap

Abstract

Mangrove Forest which is located at Karang Talun village, Tritih Kulon sub-district, North Cilacap, Central Java has a various potentials to develop. Its development can be conducted by utilizing local community for participating to improve with mastery of English language. Thus, it is necessary to conduct empowerment of local community through English language training to create qualified ones who can support in tourism field. The purpose of this training is to improve their English language skill and increase their economy and be able to survive by being local tour guide in the New Normal. There were 15 participants consist of traders and some employees who work in Mangrove forest. It was conducted for three days and used some methods, namely preaching method i.e, giving theory and practice learning on each unit of learning and drilling and repetition method. In addition, they were given pre test and post test to evaluate each participant's skill. From the result, the participant's skill in pronunciation, vocabulary and practicing dialogue has improved, but it still needs more practices. Drilling and repetition method in learning activity has been success to be applied for participants.

Keyword :English language training, local community, drilling and repetition method.

Subject :

[AR-0065]

**Test Of Heart Attack Monitoring System And Temperature Using
Whitebox Graph Matrix Method And Cyclomatic Complexity.
(AC-0872 Cahya Vikasari / Politeknik Negeri Cilacap), (AC-0873 Purwiyanto
/ Politeknik Negeri Cilacap),**

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0086 Cahya Vikasari)

Politeknik Negeri Cilacap

Abstract

Temperature monitoring system and patients heart attack is a system wich can improve the hospital service. The phase of device development which has conducted in making temperature monitoring system and patients heart attack used waterfall, one of them is testing phase. Tehe method that used to do test phase is whitebox method using cyclomatic complexity and graph matrix approach. The test will be conducted in monitoring process, whose input comes from heart attack tool and patients temperature that will send data to system. The result from the test system using cyclomatic approach is to give information the number of minimal tests and it is conducted by doing the test. In addition, the result of graph matrix test is probability edge that will be conducted.

Keyword : whitebox, graph matrix, cyclomatic.

Subject :

[AR-0072]

E-Learning As A Response To COVID-19 Pandemic: A Preliminary Study On College Students

(AC-0538 Siska Ayu Kartika /),

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0087 Siska Ayu Kartika)

Universitas Balikpapan

Abstract

There is a dilemma of accepting the new educational system, that we know as e-learning by students within educational institutions. We have to replace face-to-face education with distance education in response to the COVID-19. This form of distance education, e-learning, differs from conventional education: being suddenly, unready and forcefully implemented. This study examined and assessed the impact of e-learning to college students, during pandemic. An online survey was conducted amongst some college students in the Mechanical Engineering Dept, at Universitas Balikpapan using a purposive sampling technique. Data were analyzed using Partial Least Square - Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). The result of this study has confirmed the positive of direct effect variables (attitude, affect and motivation; perceived behavioral intention (ease of use technology, accessibility and cognitive engagement). This study suggests relevant parties to the education system, to improve the implementation of e-learning systems.

Keyword : COVID-19 pandemic, online survey, e-learning

Subject :

[AR-0062]

Survey Research On Lecturer Performance Profiles During Pandemic Covid-19

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Muhammad Yusuf / Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe Tuban),***

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0083 DUMIYATI)

Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe Tuban

Abstract

This study aims to describe the performance profile of lecturers based on the results of monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of teaching, research and community service activities during the Covid-19 pandemic. Data collection techniques used survey methods on the implementation of teaching learning process and documentation techniques in the form of lecturer performance targets and reports. Research respondents were all 216 students of the Economic Education Study Program at Unirow Tuban. Data analysis techniques used descriptive data analysis by calculating the percentage of respondents' answers, average score and categorization. The findings of the study showed that the average score was <3.5, the teaching performance of the lecturers was <4.5 in good category. Average research performance and community service in the moderate category. The results of this study can be used to follow up on learning improvements and make online learning more effective and improve the performance of lecturers in the field of research and community service activities during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Keyword : lecturer performance, online learning, research, covid-19

Subject :

[AR-0013]

The Timeliness Of Basic Immunization In Infants Related To The Knowledge About Covid-19

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Husada Kediri), (AC-0885 Layudha Ikhroma / Midwifery Study Program, School of Health Sciences Karya Husada Kediri),

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0009 Brivian Florentis Yustanta)

STIKES Karya Husada Kediri

Abstract

Abstract. During the covid-19 pandemic, many parents are worried about providing basic immunizations for their infants. This caused the basic immunization coverage at Gandusari Public Health Service in Blitar Regency in April 2020 to decrease by 4.9%, and in May 2020 to decrease by 19.7%. This study objective to determine the correlation of knowledge about covid-19 and the timeliness of basic immunization in infants. This research was analytic correlational with cross sectional study approach. The independent variable was knowledge about covid-19, while the dependent variable was the timeliness of basic immunization in infants. The population were all parents who had infants as many as 87 parents. This study using simple random sampling. The sample size was 71 parents. The instruments were maternal and child health book and questionnaires. The data were analyzed using chi square test. The results showed that p value $0.001 < 0.05$ that there were any correlation of knowledge about covid-19 and the timeliness of basic immunization in infants. The sufficient knowledge of parents about covid-19 made parents hesitate to immunize their infants. Providing basic immunization to infants during a pandemic is not prohibited as long as they comply with health protocols.

Keyword : Timeliness, Basic Immunization, Infant, Knowledge, Covid-19.

Subject : Health

[AR-0142]

The Ecological Impact Of The Covid-19 Infodemic Discourse In Social Media: An Ecolinguistic Perspective

(AC-0868 Khusnul Khotimah / Universitas Negeri Surabaya), (AC-0869 Kisyani Laksono, Suhartono, Udjang Pairin, Darni / Universitas Negeri Surabaya),

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0148 Khusnul Khotimah)

Universitas Negeri Surabaya

Abstract

Texts on social media often highlight the COVID-19 pandemic. The text influences the mindset and mode of the readers. The current problem of COVID-19 is not only deal with the virus itself, but also obstacle that is no less important facing the community is overcoming infodemics. During this pandemic, infodemics emerged. Information is redundant and untraceable, especially circulating and developing during a health emergency situation. The purpose of this study is to describe the constructive and destructive impact of infodemic discourse on readers. Data sourced from social media (Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter). The method used in this research is a qualitative approach with descriptive methods. The results showed that the ecological impact that was constructive in the content, meaning or message could influence the mindset and attitudes of readers to participate in preserving the environment. Positive texts can change negative environmental ethics into positive ones. The destructive impact is the use of sentences in the infodemic discourse in the form of text that is too clear, obscure, exaggerated, and too detailed. In addition, misinformation on health can exacerbate outbreaks of infectious diseases. Especially damaging advice can be classified as false information made with no respect for accuracy and is often integrated with narratives framed by emotion or conspiracy. The text affects attitudes and mindsets so that it damages the environment.

Keyword : ecological impact, infodemic discourse, covid-19 pandemic, ecolinguistics

Subject : Communication Science, COVID 19

[AR-0030]

Behavior Abstinence From Eating Protein And Healing Of Perineal Wounds In Postpartum

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Bachelor Midwifery Study Program Of STIKES Karya H

Abstract

This study aims to determine the Correlation between the behavior of abstinence from protein food and the duration of healing of perineal wounds in postpartum mothers. The research method used in this research is analytical research. The approach used in this research is a cross sectional sample of 45 respondents with accidental sampling technique. Data were collected using observation sheets and restructuring interview guides. The results of the analysis obtained a correlation coefficient value of 0.676 with a moderate level of relationship, which means that there is a relationship between eating stick behavior and the duration of healing of perineal wounds in postpartum mothers. Health workers, especially midwives, should provide more information, especially foods that should be consumed by postpartum mothers.

Keyword : Abstinence from eating protein, perineal wound

Subject : Health

[AR-0063]

**Synthesis And Characterization Of Eugenol-silica Gel Composites
From Corn Cob Ash And Analysis Of Water Absorption
(AC-0882 Muhammad Fathurrahman / Pakuan University), (AC-0883 Usep
Suhendar / Pakuan University),**

*Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0039 Muhammad Fathurrahman)
Universitas Pakuan*

Abstract

This study aims to make eugenol-silica gel composites with corncob ash as a base material and to analyze water absorption. Corn cobs are a material that has a high enough silica content, 67.41% of the total ash. Corn cobs ash is then used to make eugenol-silica gel composites. The method used is the sol-gel method. The eugenol-silica gel composites were characterized by FTIR (Fourier Transform Infra Red). The results of characterization using FTIR showed that the synthesis of eugenol-silica gel composites was successful. The results of the water absorption test showed that the eugenol-silica gel composite had a higher water absorption than food grade silica gel.

Keyword : eugenol-silica gel, corn cob ash, water absorption

Subject :

[AR-0097]

Web-Based Instrument Development Workshop As Supporting Materials For Online Learning

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Universitas Negeri Malang

Abstract

The development of information and communication technology is currently driving the development of internet networks around the world. This internet can be useful in various fields including education. Education is currently experiencing system changes as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. The learning is carried out online. Therefore, it takes teacher skills in preparing online learning media. Based on this, a web-based instrument development workshop activity was carried out for science teachers in the IPA MGMP of Jombang Regency. The number of participants was 65 science teachers in the IPA MGMP of Jombang Regency. The workshop was held for three days online via the zoom platform. The first two days were the delivery of learning video development materials using the OBS application, google form, quizizz and google classroom then the participants worked independently. The third day was a presentation of the participants' independent work. The workshop participants were enthusiastic about participating in the workshop as seen from the post-workshop survey results. This workshop resulted in 60 web-based instrument products and articles on the development of participant instruments

Keyword :learning instruments, web-based learning instrument, online learning, COVID-19.

Subject :

[AR-0121]

Alcohol And Khamr On Fiqh Using Science Experiment Videos In Schools Affected By COVID-19

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0138 Suyadi)

Ahmad Dahlan University

Abstract

Covid-19 has paralyzed Islamic and Natural Science Education in Indonesia. The impact of online learning is not optimal, teachers have difficulty explaining the material or practice making it more difficult for students to understand the material. The purpose of this study was to improve the students' understanding of grade 8 PGRI 6 Denpasar Junior High School on fiqh regarding alcohol and khamr with online learning. The media used is a science experiment video which will have implications for changing the way students perceive the use of alcohol and khamr. This study uses the Nonequivalent Control Group Design method with a comparison between the science experiment class and the control class using the traditional method. The results of the validation of experimental experts, 91.34% fiqh material with perfect criteria. Pretest in the experimental class percentage of 70% sufficient criteria from the experimental class and the control class get a presentation of 72.4% sufficient criteria. Posttest in the experimental class with a percentage of 87.4% good criteria while in the control class presentation 75%.Based on the results of the validation and pretest-posttest comparisons between classes, the experimental method is good for learning fiqh in Islamic education.

Keyword :online teaching and learning, COVID-19, fiqh, alcohol and khamr, islamic education

Subject : Education

[AR-0052]

Application Of Behavioral Architecture Concept On Space Order Natural Laboratory

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Universitas Widya Kartika

Abstract

Elementary school natural laboratory is one of the learning facilities for students to produce a quality learning process. The laboratory is also a place for teaching and learning through practicum methods that interact and observe with living things directly. This natural laboratory is designed with a spatial layout based on the concept of behavioral architecture. The location of this research in Nation Star Academy Elementary School, Surabaya. Natural laboratories are very important in supporting Science subjects so that teachers can be optimal in explaining natural science in real terms. The research method used are qualitative and analytical. The data used in these methods consist of literature studies, interviews, observations of similar objects, and documentation. The result of this research is the design of a natural laboratory as a support for Elementary School Science subjects with the concept of behavioral architectural design in space order laboratory, which directs user behavior in achieving more ergonomic and efficient space requirements.

Keyword : Natural Laboratory, Space Order, Behavioral Architecture

Subject :

[AR-0150]

**Social Mapping Of Cultural Production: Strategies In Dealing With
The Decline In Tourism Due To The Covid19 Pandemic In
Panglipuran Village, Bali**

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*Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0151 I Wayan Gede Lamopia, Riza Wulandari
, Isma Illia Shara Yunianti)*

Institute Technology And Business STIKOM Bali

Abstract

Panglipuran village is a reflection of Balinese in the field of tourism. In anticipating the decrease of visitors in Panglipuran due to the covid19 pandemic, it is necessary to conduct a scientific study, namely social mapping of cultural production. The study aims to ease the people in Panglipuran village to explore the potential of the village to recover economic condition due to the decrease of tourists. Based on the bordieu paradigm and field observation, there are four potential assets in dealing with the crisis, namely symbolic, cultural, economic, and social assets

Keyword : Social Mapping, Cultural Production, Tourism, Covid19 Pandemic, Panglipuran Village Bali

Subject : Management

[AR-0148]

**Local Management Conflict Resolution Among Elementary
Schools Principals In Maguindanao**
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Philippines),*

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Cotabato City State Polytechnic College

Abstract

The basic function of school principal is to resolve conflicts and this needs skillful principals to handle those problems, to come up with peaceful solutions and outcomes. The main focus of the study was to determine the Local Management Conflict Resolution among Elementary Schools Principals in Maguindanao. The descriptive correlation method of research was used in this study. It was conducted at 20 Central Elementary Schools in Maguindanao -1 Division with a total of 150 teachers participated in the study. The data gathered were analyzed using SPSS. The statistical tools used were weighted average mean and regression analysis. The Level of Conflict Resolution Skills of Elementary Schools Principals in Maguindanao were rated negotiated that described their skills in conflict resolution in terms of negotiation with a grand mean of 3.42, Mediation were rated highly mediated with a grand mean of 3.57. The Extent of conflict management of the Elementary Schools Principals in the Province of Maguindanao to manage conflict of teachers vs teachers were rated satisfactory with a grand mean of 3.31, teachers vs pupils 3.35. Moreover, the conflict resolution skills of elementary schools principals in Maguindanao were manifested and conflicts were managed most of the time by the principals. The influence between the levels of conflict resolution skills of elementary schools principals in Maguindanao to principals' management was Significant. It is recommended that conflict resolution skills of elementary schools principals in Maguindanao need to improve and strengthen it for self-development to manage all the time the conflicts very well.

Keyword : Conflict Resolution Skills, Local Management, Negotiation and Mediation

Subject : Education

[AR-0076]

Measurement And Analysis Of Differences In The Impact Of The Implementation Of Large-Scale Social Restrictions Based On The Mann Whitney Test.

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UNIVERSITAS SURABAYA

Abstract

This research is a non-parametric statistical measurement form which use the Mann Whitney test. The aim is to determine whether or not there are differences in the impact of the implementation of the PSBB as a result of COVID-19 pandemic in the Surabaya, Gresik and Sidoarjo areas through the distribution of questionnaires and interviews, a sample of 134 people who were distributed in the 3 regions obtained. From the results of repeated simulations, measurements and testing to answer existing hypotheses, it can be seen that there are 3 things that are the conclusions of this study. The first conclusion, that there is no difference in the impact of the PSBB implementation in the Sidoarjo and Surabaya areas, which use $\hat{\alpha} = 5\%$, the value obtained $Z_{count} = -0.65745$ is higher than $Z_{table} = \pm 1.96$. It is in the receiving area which means H_0 or the hypothesis that there is no difference in the impact of the PSBB implementation between Sidoarjo and Surabaya areas cannot be rejected. The second conclusion, that there are differences in the impact of the PSBB implementation in the Surabaya and Gresik areas with the result that the value of $Z_{count} = -2.28792$ is lower than Z_{table} . The same thing happened in the third test, there was a significant difference in the impact of the PSBB implementation in Sidoarjo and Gresik areas. Furthermore, in the descriptive analysis, there are several factors were found which effect the three tests result, as follows: geographic, demographic, social, cultural and employment factors.

Keyword : impact, PSBB, mann whitney test

Subject :

[AR-0016]

**The Effect Of Effleurage Massage On Pain Reduction In Mothers
During The First Phase Of The Active Labour**

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0022 Dewi Taurisiawati Rahayu)

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine whether there was an effect of effleurage massage on reducing pain in the first stage of the inpartum mother in Independent midwifery practice Mrs. Muhartik, Kandangan Village, Kediri Regency. This study used a pre-experimental method with a one group pre-test post-test design on July 20 to August 8 2020, the number of samples in this study were 13 intra partum mothers, using accidental sampling technique. The instrument in this study used the rules of procedure and questionnaires. By using the Wilcoson sign rank statistical test, it was obtained that there is an effect of effleurage massage on pain reduction in inpartum mothers during the first phase of the active phase. Effleurage massage can be given to mothers in labor during the first active phase when a contraction is given to the 5th lumbar back with a duration of 20 minutes. Keywords: Effleurage Massage, Pain in Intrapartum Mother.

Keyword : Effleurage Massage, Pain in Intrapartum Mother.

Subject : Health

[AR-0124]

**RISK BASED IMPROVEMENT PERFORMANCE STRATEGY FOR
OPERATION AND MAINTENANCE ACTIVITIES OF RIVER AND
RIVER INFRASTRUCTURE (BBWS CILIWUNG-CISADANE
AUTHORITY)**

(AC-0726 Isni Septima Anindhita / Universitas Indonesia),

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Universitas Indonesia

Abstract

The Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing (PUPR) has the duty and responsibility to carry out operation and maintenance of rivers and river infrastructure effectively and efficiently including overcoming floods in the rainy season. However, seeing the frequent flood disasters is an indicator that this activity is not yet optimal in dealing with flooding. To improve the performance of operation and maintenance of rivers and river infrastructure that have been built, it is necessary to improve planning procedures and researchers intending to carry out risk management in this activity. Risk management begins by identifying a list of risks that can reduce the performance of rivers and river infrastructure as flood control. Then the list of risks obtained will be processed using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). The results of data analysis are in the form of risk categories which will be analyzed to determine the priority scale order of risks that occur and risk management is determined which is then used as a risk-based development strategy in the form of action recommendations (risk response) to improve performance of river and river infrastructure to control flooding through operation and maintenance activities in order to build a functional and sustainable system for long-term planning and short-term maintenance needs.

Keyword : River, Operation and Maintenance, Risk Management

Subject :

**Study Of The Use Of Block Compos On The Growth Of Teak
(Tectona Grandis) In Used Lands Of Kapur Stone Mine
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Sriwulan / Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe), (AC-0758 Ahmad Zaenal Arifin /
Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe), (AC-0759 Eko Purnomo / PT Semen
Indonesia Tbk), (AC-0760 Aris Santoso / PT Konsulta Semen Gresik), (AC-
0761 Ali Mustofa / Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe),**

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Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe

The limestone mining area is a karst area that has an important ecological function as a water conservation area. After the mining process, the ex-mining area becomes critical land that is poor in nutrients, decreases soil microbial diversity, increases soil pH and temperature, and has a compact soil structure. this study aimed to examine the use of conventional and block compost based on plant height parameters and plant growth diameter. Block compost was made using the bokashi method with the basic ingredient of teak leaf litter (*Tectona grandis*). The composition of leaf litter (30%), manure (40%), and sawdust (30%). Block compost is made by adding adhesive and it is made using a pressing device. The conclusion of this study is the use of block compost application on plants is very effective compared to planting plants without block compost (conventional). The plant height and stem growth diameter of the block compost system had higher yields than the conventional system. This shows that block compost is a solution in mining land reclamation.

Keyword :mine land, block compost, conventional compost, growth of plant height and plant diameter.

Subject : Agriculture

[AR-0120]

A Level Of Student Self Discipline In E-Learning During Pandemic Covid-19

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Universiti Utara Malaysia

Abstract

Self-discipline in academics is the firmness of students in training themselves to be better in their learning. E-learning is now a growing learning method in every corner of the globe. It is able to speed up teaching and make the learning process last a lifetime. In Malaysia, the effectiveness of e-learning among school students may differ from IPT students where e-learning has a positive impact on IPT students. It was found that not many studies have been done on high school students related to distance education using e-learning methods. This quantitative descriptive study was conducted to find out the level of self-discipline of secondary school students in the world of e-learning during the period of the Covid-19 Movement Control Order in Malaysia as well as its relationship with gender and academic performance. The sample of this study was randomly selected consisting of 165 respondents of upper secondary students in Form Four and Five at SMK Syed Sirajuddin, Perlis. To achieve the objectives of this study, a questionnaire was used to collect research information and data was analyzed with the help of Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS version 26). Overall, the results of the mean calculation found that the level of self-discipline of students is at a moderate level. The results of the ttest found that there was no significant difference between the level of self-discipline of students based on gender. Meanwhile, Pearson correlation test proves that students' level of self-discipline also affects their academic performance. At the end of this writing, some suggestions have been put forward. Finally, this study has an impact not only on the world of education where teaching and learning are in new norms but also on the world of information technology to further develop interactive learning.

Keyword : self-discipline, e-learning, academic performance, secondary school, Covid-19

[AR-0061]

Minimizing Disease Spread Of Quarantined Covid-19 With Asymptomatic Infections In Indonesia

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

In early March 2020, the Covid-19 pandemic happened in Indonesia. It changes the major public health, social, and economy. The first case is discovered in two resident of Depok, West Java, in Indonesia. Continuously, the number of residents who tested positive for the Corona virus reached 1.155 and 102 of them died. The cases that happened in Indonesia were caused by the large number of residents who did not obey health protocol and social distancing. So that, the variables of this models merge of the roles of environmental contamination by Covid-19 and the infected individuals who quarantined. The parameters is using cumulative mortality data from Indonesia caused Covid-19. It measures the impact of various control and the spread of quarantined Covid-19 infections. The analysis of the models reveals that disease-free equilibrium is asymptotically stable although the control reproduction number is less than unity. The quarantined Covid-19 that asymptomatic infection indicated are not identified. The epidemiological implication of this result is that the disease will eventually die out by controlling the action early and continuously. In minimizing the number of cases, our study emphasizes to the important of surveillance testing, contact tracing of the contacts, and confirm cases in Indonesia.

Keyword : quarantined, infections, asymptomatic

Subject :

[AR-0035]

ONLINE CBT AND ELIP EFFECTIVENESS AGAINST THE DEGREE OF POST PARTUM BLUES IN MADURA URBAN

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Correspondent author :

(RJI-1-0043 Elly Dwi

Masita) Unusa

Abstract

A preliminary study in February 2020 in northern Surabaya explained that 81% of post partum mothers experienced post partum blues. This condition has an impact on increasing the morbidity and mortality rates for mothers and newborns. This research to aim to know differences between the CBT and ELIP methods on the degree of post partum blues in the urban Madurese in Surabaya. Type of research is quantitative with a non equivalent control group with design experimental approach. The population was 80 postpartum mothers. Sampling used a total sampling of 40 as pre and post CBT groups and 40 as pre and post ELIP groups. Instrument used EPDS through online screening, while CBT and ELIP were carried out through online web. Analysis test used pair t test and independent t test with $p < 0.05$. Result and implication has showing that are differences in the pre and post groups in each group of CBT of 22.87 and ELIP of 22.95, while independent t test has obtaine $p = 0.81$ it is mean that there is not differences in both CBT and ELIP in reducing the degree of post partum blues.

Keyword : CBT, ELIP, Online, Post partum Blues

Subject : Health Science

[AR-0014]

**Analysis Of Students' Critical Thinking Abilities Using The
PDEODE Strategy In Terms Of Cognitive Style Through Online
Learning**

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Tuban), (AC-0697 Hernik Puji***

*Astuti / Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe Tuban), (AC-0698 Imas Cintamulya /
Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe Tuban),*

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Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe Tuban

Abstract. The existence of the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020 resulted in learning being carried out on-line. However, critical thinking skills are still honed in the learning process. The purpose of this study was to obtain a description of the critical thinking skills of students of Mathematics Education 2019, PGRI Ronggolawe Tuban University in the Environmental Knowledge course using the PDEODE strategy on the Reflective cognitive style and Impulsive cognitive style. This type of research is descriptive exploratory research. Data collection techniques used MFFT (Matching Familiar Figures Test (MFFT) and critical thinking ability tests. The research subjects were 12 students. The results showed that: 1) There were 5 students with a reflective cognitive style and 7 students with an impulsive cognitive style. 2) The average results of critical thinking skills for all aspects of critical thinking components in the reflective cognitive style group, 40% for high category, 20% for moderate category, 40% for low category, while 28.6% for high category impulsiveness, 28.6% medium category, and 42.8% low category. The conclusion is that the PDEODE strategy can be applied to learning to empower critical thinking skills in terms of reflective and impulsive cognitive styles

Keyword : critical thinking, PDEODE, cognitive style

Subject : Education

[AR-0117]

**ELECTRONIC WORD OF MOUTH DURING ADAPTATION PANDEMIC
COVID-19 TOWARDS THE NEW NORMAL : Cases In Indonesia
(AC-0839 Novi Andayani Praptiningsih / UHAMKA),**

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0132 Novi Andayani Praptiningsih)

University Muhammadiyah Prof. Dr. HAMKA

Abstract

In this digitalization era the role of Electronic Word of Mouth (e-WOM) is very useful especially during the conditions of the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak. e-WoM is a form of marketing communication that contains positive or negative statements made by potential customers, customers or ex-customers about a product or company. Large-Scale Social Limitation Policy in a number of regions in Indonesia in order to cut off transmission corona virus is driving skyrocketing use and demand for online transaction services because when the Covid-19 pandemic emerged, almost all human activity was restricted. The policy plan for the implementation of new normal in Indonesia due to economic reasons is slowing, there are still many concerns of some Indonesian people because many are lacking discipline by not heeding health protocols, such as keeping a distance, not crowding, using masks, and washing hands / handsanitizer. Always think positively and adhere to the health protocol of the pandemic period as a solution to community members not easily infected by the covid pandemic 19 epidemic that has not yet gone and become extinct from Indonesia and the world. Even though the activities that have to run are not normal, we can still take lessons from the events behind this pandemic.

Keyword : electronic word of mouth, adaptation, covid 19, new normal

Subject : Communication Science, COVID19

[AR-0102]

NOVICE TEACHERS' NEEDS IN STARTING CAREER AS AN EDUCATOR

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0120 MOHD ISHA AWANG)

Universiti Utara Malaysia

Abstract

A new teacher is an individual who has just started a career in the field of teaching with less than three years of experience. They need certain aspects as a new teacher in starting a career as a teacher. This requirement is an important aspect that will contribute to the effectiveness of their teaching in the classroom. A study aimed at identifying the needs of new teachers starting this career using a survey research design. The questionnaire was used as a research instrument to review a simple randomly selected study sample involving 177 new teachers. The study found several aspects that are necessary for new teachers such as mentoring aspects, school support, key information, teaching and learning practices and co-curricular activities. This study has important implications to the school, State Educational Department and Ministry of Education in providing ongoing support to new teachers and then to develop their level of professionalism in the classroom in particular and in the education profession in general.

Keyword :New Teacher, mentoring, teaching and learning, co-curriculum activities, school support

Subject : Education

[AR-0050]

Model Of Application Of Technology To Increase Income In Micro Business Clover Stick In The Face Of Covid-19 Pandemic Era

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0050 Hendrik Rizqiawan)

Universitas Wijaya Putra

Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic caused a heavy problem for many businesses, not least in partners who are micro-entrepreneurs. The micro business clover stick, which is run by a group of housewives in Lakarsantri Village, Surabaya, was severely affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. Even in the early months of the pandemic, their business were not operational. Stick clover that they produce is not the main choice to buy for the people who are around the partner location. This is possible because so far partners have only marketed their products around their region, partners have not taken advantage of the availability of digital technology in marketing. In addition, partners have been conducting production processes with conventional equipment and as is. This is considered less effective and results in some partner members choosing other activities that are more yielding. With the right technology implementation model, both in the production and marketing process, partners are experiencing a rise in income. If before the pandemic, the income generated by partners at 500 thousand to 1 million per month, after using the technology implementation model partners can get a income of 2 million more in one month.

Keyword : Empowerment; Entrepreneurship; Self-Reliance; Surabaya

Subject :

[AR-0093]

**EMPOWERMENT BASED ON NON-FORMAL EDUCATION
THROUGH LOCAL POTENTIAL IN LAMPUNG COFFEE PROCESSING
(AC-0459 lintang markhamah watianur azizah / universitas negeri
semarang),**

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AZIZAH)*

UNIVERSITAS NEGERI SEMARANG

Abstract

The Covid 19 has caused all sectors to weaken. Strength of region can be built through economic recovery of each region which is supported by empowerment education program as utilization of regional potential. The purpose of study is to provide results of developing entrepreneurship skills in students of PAKET C equivalency program based on local potential through Lampung coffee processing training. skills provided include production and marketing of Lampung coffee into processed foods such as biscuits, air freshener, and ready-to-brew ground coffee. Marketing of Lampung coffee products has been marketed throughout Indonesia and even abroad. Research uses qualitative descriptive approach which is defined as problem-solving procedure by describing the subject or object situation (person, institution, or society) based on real conditions. Data collection using the method of observation, interviews, documentation correspondence, as well as literature reviews of relevant research to obtain secondary data. The data were analyzed using qualitative descriptive. Result of research is that students have skills to produce and market Lampung coffee at PKBM Kencana. Each month each student gets an income of 2 until 3 million. This research makes a scientific contribution to the study of non-formal education that leads to the quality of education in society.

Keyword : Community empowerment; Community Learning Center PKBM, Entrepreneurship Development;Local Potential.

Subject :Community Development

[AR-0106]

**Prevalence Of Parasites In Freshwater Fishes In Southern Part Of
Ligawasan Marsh, Philippines**

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College),**

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Cotabato City State Polytechnic College

Abstract

Ligawasan Marsh, the largest river basin in Mindanao is home of common fishes such as dalag, pupuyo, hito, tilapia and gourami. Fish parasites pose a great threat to freshwater fishes to public health and economy of an area. This study aims to examine the Prevalence of Parasites in Freshwater Fishes in the Southern Part of Ligawasan Marsh; Endoparasites in the representative species; Mean intensity and abundance infection of the Endoparasites, source of fish with prevalent parasites; and waste disposal practices and environmental stressors. The study utilized necropsy, dissection and microscopy method to examine Endoparasites. Trematodes *Clinostomum* sp, suspected *Camallanus* sp., a *Neocamallanus* sp. and a member of Order *Spirurida*, all nematodes were recovered. The study yielded that Fish parasites in *Channa striata* *Anabas testudineus* had prevalence in Kabuntalan and Datu Piang. Nine *Acanthocephalan* recovered in *Oreochromis niloticus* had also prevalence rate. Suspected trematode cysts and eggs were also recovered in *Trichopodus trichopterus* and *Clarias macrocephalus*. Thus, it is concluded that there is prevalence of nematodes and trematodes species in *C. striata*, *A. testudineus*, *O. niloticus*, *C. macrocephalus* and *T. trichopterus* The *Camallanus* sp and *Neocamallanus* sp, both common aquarium parasites are first found in the Southern part of Ligawasan Marsh.

Keyword : Prevalence of Parasites, Freshwater Fishes, Necropsy, Dissection and Microscopy, Ligawasan Marsh, Philippines

Subject : Science

[AR-0109]

**Empirical Evidence Of Asset Pricing Based On Single Index Model,
Fama And French Three And Five Factor Models In Indonesia
Stock Exchange**

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0127 Ani Silvia)

Universitas Muhammadiyah Prof. DR. HAMKA

Abstract

This empirical test aims to estimate the beta parameters of the risk premium and other risk factors using the Single index model, Fama and French three and five-factor models. The sample companies used as the study object are companies in the property and real estate subsector with data collected in index prices, stock prices, number of shares in circulation, 90-day SBI interest rates, and book value per share, operating profit, and also the company's total assets obtained through datastream from Thomson Reuters from January 2014 to December 2018. The results are consistent with the previous studies that asset pricing using the Fama and French five-factor model can better explain stock returns than the other two models. The property and real estate subsector seems to provide a positive and statistically significant excess return, which indicates that asset pricing with the three models is irrelevant to be applied in Indonesia. These results suggest that the stock market in Indonesia is still inefficient.

Keyword : Asset Pricing, Single index model, Fama and French three and five-factor model, risk, return

Subject :

[AR-0020]

Regularity Of Prenatal Gentle Yoga Against Back Pain In Third Trimester Pregnant Women

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Kediri), (AC-0126 Lailatul Magfiroh / Bachelor of Midwifery Study Program, School of Health Sciences Karya Husada Kediri),

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Bachelor Of Midwifery Study Program, School Of Hea

Abstract

Aim of study to determine the effect of prenatal gentle yoga on back pain in third trimester pregnant women. Pre experimental research methods. The independent variable prenatal gentle yoga, the dependent variable back pain in the third trimester of pregnant women. Population of 30 respondents, sampling purposive sampling obtained a sample of 27 respondents. Research from June-July 2020 at the Aminah General Hospital, Blitar City, analyzed data using Spearman Rank. The result of the study was 51.85% of respondents experienced mild back pain in respondents who regularly followed prenatal gentle yoga. Meanwhile, 66.67% of respondents who did not follow prenatal gentle yoga experienced severe back pain. The p value is $0.001 < \hat{\pm} 0.05$. Implication yoga can reduce back pain in pregnant women by using relaxation techniques, can maintain elasticity and strength of the pelvic ligaments, hips and leg muscles so that pregnant women can be comfortable when undergoing pregnancy.

Keyword : Prenatal gentle yoga, back pain, third trimester pregnant mother

Subject : Health

[AR-0112]

**Bachelor Of Science In Business Administration (BSBA) Graduate
Tracer Study Year 2012-2019**

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Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0128 Emraida C. Ali)

Cotabato City State Polytechnic College

Abstract

This study was conducted to trace the Cotabato City State Polytechnic College (CCSPC)-College of Business and Public Administration (CBPA) graduates in terms of their educational background, employment opportunity, and contribution of curricular program to their communication, human relations, leadership and problem solving skills. Moreover, this study was conducted in CCSPC, Sinsuat Avenue, Cotabato City. The respondents were the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration from year 2012 to 2019 and they were selected using purposive and convenience sampling. It employed quantitative research and utilized descriptive-status research design. The statistical tools used were frequency, percentage, and mean. The results revealed that majority of the respondents are single, female, and graduates of BSBA major in Marketing Management. For their employment opportunity, majority of them have been employed and in a regular or permanent employment status. In addition, they are commonly connected with these industry classifications: wholesale/trade, government, and banking and finance. The results also revealed that the curricular program contributed to the development of their communication, human relation, leadership and problem solving skills.

Keyword : curricular program, communication, human relation, leadership, and problem solving skills

Subject : Education

[AR-0132]

Integrated Validation System (IVS) Design For Proposal Submission Of Student Activities At PPNS

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Politeknik Perkapalan Negeri Surabaya

Abstract

The concept of Industry 4.0 is a combination of new technological developments that aim to facilitate human-computer interaction. Higher Education Institutions are currently not separated from the development of the industrial revolution involvement 4.0. Technology has a tremendous influence in the running of all activities of daily living, not least the performance of management in institutions of Higher Education Institutions. The demand to be able to work more effectively and efficiently in producing a product both in the form of goods and services makes PPNS have to keep up with technological developments. PPNS is expected to produce a product, both goods and services, in accordance with the expectations of the stakeholders (students, society and lecturers-employees). One of the problems that often becomes a problem is the bureaucracy that has a long flow. In this study, problems that occur in the PPNS Student Affairs Sector will be raised, namely regarding the approval of student activity proposals from the Student Association (HIMA) by the PPNS Management in Student Affairs under Deputy Director III. There are several steps that can be assisted in the process by using technology, so as to increase the effectiveness of performance in student affairs. Based on these problems and opportunities, a study is proposed with the title Integrated Validation System (IVS) Development to Optimize Student Service Performance in PPNS. With this system, it is hoped that it will help optimize the performance in the field of student affairs so that it can be more effective and efficient in serving requests for student activities at PPNS

Keyword : Integrated Validation System, technology, Design System,

Proposal Submission **Subject** : Information Technology

[AR-0111]

Drivers Of Entrepreneurship In Autonomous Region In Muslim Mindanao, Philippines

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Abstract

This is a quantitative study conducted to analyze the drivers of entrepreneurship in the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao. The descriptive-correlation research design was used to execute the research and analyze the data. The respondents were the selected women entrepreneurs in the provinces of Maguindanao, Lanao del Sur, Basilan, Sulu and Tawi-tawi. A modified research questionnaire was used in this study as the main data-gathering instrument. Data were analyzed using the frequency, percentage, mean, multiple regression analysis, and hierarchical multiple regression. The personal entrepreneurial competency, presence of entrepreneurial role model, government programs and interventions, motivation, entrepreneurial environment, and cultural orientations were studied whether they influence the extent of women entrepreneurship in terms of involvement in the four phases of entrepreneurial activity: searching; planning; marshalling; and implementing. Moreover, age and educational attainment were studied whether they offer significant contingent effect on the relationship of the dependent and independent variables. Results of the study revealed that significant predictors are the personal entrepreneurial competency, government programs and interventions, motivation, and entrepreneurial environment. And the best predictor of women entrepreneurship is government programs and interventions. Moreover, the age and educational attainment have no significant contingent effect on the relationship of the dependent and independent variables.

Keyword : Women Entrepreneurship, Government Programs and Interventions, Personal Entrepreneurial Competency

Subject :Entrepreneurship

[AR-0147]

**Introducing New And Innovative Modes Of Instruction And
Framework For The Establishment Of Institution's
Authority, Accountability And Responsibility Throughout The
Covid-19 Crisis**

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Abstract

Change happens even at the blink of an eye according to an enthusiast whereas science says, "Nothing is constant in this world except change." The "new normal" condition brought about by the Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic has ignited the study to promptly navigate the extent and relationship of introducing new and innovative modes of instruction and providing framework for the establishment of the institution's authority, accountability and responsibility during this crisis specifically in the fourth industrial revolution in South Central Mindanao using quantitative-descriptive as well as correlational and regression methods and designs. At least 220 respondents covering the principals and teachers have been selected using the total enumeration sampling technique. The study has utilized Mean, Pearson r Correlation and Multiple Regression (Stepwise) as statistical tools in the analysis of quantitative data. The findings revealed that the extent of introducing new and innovative modes of instruction as well as the extent of providing framework for the establishment of the institution's authority, accountability and responsibility in the COVID-19 crisis has been highly evident. Correlational analysis between the introduction of new and innovative modes of instruction and providing framework for the establishment of the institution's authority, accountability and responsibility revealed a significant relationship; hence, the null hypothesis (H_0) has been moderately rejected. The best predictors that have emerged in the overall introduction of new and innovative modes of instruction have been on linking the educational content with the experiences of teachers; using technology to enhance instruction; transforming the

teaching experience into an interactive and collaborative experience as the teachers use dynamic multimedia content; using various tools of technology the students are encouraged; using innovative method of teaching that involves encouraging student collaboration for various projects; fostering skills by allowing students to learn, study and work independently; offering virtual reality technology as a valuable opportunity; and using the 3D printers to teach content; thus, the null hypothesis (HO2) has been partially rejected. The study has concluded that the institutional leaders have been very innovative in addressing the challenges during these times of crisis. Institutionalizing policies to ensure the smooth operation of the school and sustainability of the school programs and activities to attain desirable learning outcomes is highly recommended even in times of crisis; hence, the show must go on. Keywords: modes of instruction, authority, accountability, responsibility, COVID-19 crisis

Keyword : modes of instruction, authority, accountability, responsibility, COVID-19 crisis

Subject : Public Administration

[AR-0107]

**Detection Of Tax Avoidance Due To The COVID-19 Pandemic With
The Tax Aggressiveness Model**

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Universitas Pancasila

Abstract

Tax aggressiveness is an action designed to reduce taxable income. Avoidance is done through tax planning. This study aims to analyze indications of tax avoidance with the tax aggressiveness model. Measurements are made by proxy for the abnormal book-tax differences. The way to measure it is by connecting the investment value, changes in income, fiscal, and commercial losses. The manufacturing sector is an important sector for economic recovery. The Ministry of Industry is focused on improving the performance of the five manufacturing sectors to enter the industrial era 4.0. This sector is the pillar of future national economic growth. The five sectors include the food and beverage, textile and clothing, chemical, automotive, and electronics industries. The results of the research are expected to become a reference for policies on economic recovery after the Covid-19 pandemic, especially regarding tax policies.

Keyword : Tax Aggressiveness, Manufacturing, Book Tax Difference, Economic Policy, Covid 19

Subject : Finance and Banking

[AR-0044]

**THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPOWERMENT AND JOB
SATISFACTION ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN MAJALENGKA
REGENCY**

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UNIVERSITAS MAJALENGKA

Abstract

This study aims to see the relationship between empowerment and job satisfaction on employee performance in Majalengka Regency. This research uses a quantitative approach, with survey methods and path analysis techniques. The sample in this study were employees in the Majalengka environment with a sample size of 80 employees. The data collection technique in this research is by using a questionnaire containing several lists of statements. The results showed that (1) employee performance was directly affected by empowerment. Increased empowerment would result in an increase in performance of 3.2%. (2) Increased job satisfaction will result in an increase in employee performance by 19%. (3) job satisfaction is directly affected by empowerment, increasing empowerment will result in an increase in satisfaction by 12%.

Keyword : empowerment, job satisfaction, employee performance

Subject :

[AR-0031]

**Physiotherapy Management To Prevention Of Covid-19 By
Improved Physical Activity In Elderly
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Ade Irma Nahdliyyah / Pekalongan University),**

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Pekalongan University

Abstract

Abstract Background. Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19), is an acute respiratory syndrome caused by the corona-2 virus (SARS-CoV-2). Elderly is a condition where the tissue's ability to repair itself or replace itself slowly disappears and maintains its normal structure and function so that it cannot survive. Problems that may arise, it is necessary to improve or improve the physical condition of the elderly, which can help them to maintain their health in their retirement. This study aims to reduce the impact of the Covid 19 pandemic on the elderly, provide an overview of the physical problems of Covid 19 in the elderly and prevention of Covid 19 in the elderly Materials and methods This type of research is a type of experimental research that uses a pre-experimental research design in the form of a one-group pretest-posttest design. Results showed a probability value with a value of $p < 0.05$. These results indicate that physiotherapy management in the elderly during Covid 19 provided support for increased physical activity, so that the risk of being exposed to Covid 19 can be eliminated. Conclusions management physiotherapy for covid 19 the p value is 0.000, p value < 0.05 , this shows that there are significant results between the pre test and post test on the physiotherapy management of the elderly during the Covid 19 pandemic. For the physical activity for elderly the p value is 0,015 this shows that the physical activities carried out by the elderly during a pandemic have not changed but can be given motivation to do physical activity. For the information fear of contracting corona virus p value 0,007 this shows that the information on physical activity provided by physiotherapy does not change the fear of the elderly still being exposed to Covid

Keyword : Covid 19, Elderly Physical Activity, PASE Scale

Subject :

[AR-0143]

**BUSINESS INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY MODELS FOR WOMEN
FARMER GROUP IN INDONESIA**

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Departemen Aktuaria ITS

Abstract

The existence of women farmer groups in the use of land for agriculture, such as existing fruit and vegetables, deserves a response to the follow-up, considering that the activities of women farmer groups have great potential. However, their professions as farmers and agricultural laborers income does not necessarily depend on the season. With the ability to manage further processed agricultural products, they can have reliable income and use a marketing system that is adjusted to the times. This research is a model trial with the aim of minimizing disparities in the village. By utilizing knowledge, skills and technology, it is hoped that poverty and disparity can be minimized or even eliminated. This research at a macro level provides benefits to stakeholders, namely human resources who supply raw materials, female farmers who are metamorphosed into entrepreneurs, so that domestic and foreign consumers will get superior regional products with high quality.

Keyword : agriculture, women farmer, business information, disparities, consumers

Subject : Community Development

[AR-0134]

**Teachersâ€™ Strategies In Promoting Awareness And Developing
Competence During Covid 19 Online Learning**

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UHAMKA

Abstract

The goal of this case study is to explore the way the teachers promote critical awareness of the students in primary and secondary schools during work from home phase of Covid 19 and report the students reaction about the strategies utilized by the teachers. Text and series of short story videos created by the students and the teachers were used to motivate the students to learn English as well as being aware of the Covid 19 pandemic. Five teachers from 3 different schools, teaching different subjects around Jakarta and Tangerang were involve in. Interesting panic reactions from parents and teacher were noted. The teachersâ€™ strategies in overcoming challenges and utilizing the strength of the online learning in developing students. Competece in English and other subjects are vary. Studentsâ€™ anthusiasm in giving responses online to the questioning strategies are part of the sign of critical awareness development.

Keyword : Teachersâ€™ strategies, critical awareness, online learning

Subject : Education

[AR-0058]

The Effectiveness Of RADEC As A Distance Learning Model To Improve The Understanding Of Senior High School Students On Dynamic Fluid Materials

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Universitas Negeri Malang

Abstract

During distance learning, many teachers have problems providing material, one of which is dynamic fluid material, so that students have difficulty understanding the material. The Read-Answer-Discuss-Explain-Create (RADEC) learning model is an innovative learning model. This study aims to determine the RADEC learning model's effectiveness in improving the understanding of dynamic fluid material to class XI Senior High School (SHS). This study used quasiexperimental research. The population was all students of XI SHS classes, totaling 154 people. The sampling technique used purposive sampling. The sample is XI-3 class as the control class and XI-4 class as the experimental class. The instrument used was a cognitive test. The data analysis technique used descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The results showed that the two groups' average value is that the pretest control class was 58.12, and the post-test was 78.13, while the pretest and post-test experimental class was 76.72 and 87.19. Based on the independent sample t-test, the value of $\text{sig} = 0.002 < \alpha = 0.05$, which can be concluded that there is a difference in the average class XI SHS in understanding dynamic fluid material using the RADEC learning model. The RADEC learning model is more effective than the conventional learning model.

Keyword : RADEC Learning Model, Distance Learning, Students' understanding

Subject : Education

[AR-0125]

Ways To Develop Infrastructure Of Tourism Destinations
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Abstract

This article explores the theoretical aspects of coordinating the management of infrastructure components in the development of tourism destinations and the practical state of the infrastructure in destinations. Based on the analysis, proposals have been developed based on international experience in the development of tourism infrastructure.

Keyword : Tourism destinations, tourism infrastructure, destination quality, evaluation criteria.

Subject :

[AR-0126]

Problems Of Employment In The Republic Of Uzbekistan
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University And «Silk Road» International Univers

Abstract

This article analyzes the issues of unemployment and poverty in our country and identifies its causes. Foreign experience was studied in order to compare the living standards of the population. Proposals have been developed on ways to increase employment and mechanisms for its implementation.

Keyword : unemployment, poverty, low income, standard of living, employment, well-being, supply

Subject :

[AR-0128]

Development Of The Tourism Industry Before And After The Covid Pandemic

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Abstract

This article examines the development of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan before and after the pandemic. A detailed analysis of the development of tourism for many years before the pandemic was made. It is widely known that many travel companies, their owners, managers and employees found themselves in a very difficult situation. The authors tried to analyze and give their forecasts, as well as recommendations for the further development of the tourism industry.

Keyword : tourism , Covid , pandemic

Subject :

[AR-0127]

Ict And Economic Growth Nexus: Case Of Central Asian Countries
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Abstract

The Government of Uzbekistan declared the year of 2020 as “The Year of Science, Education and Development of the Digital Economy” and is implementing the State Program, aiming at to liberalize the economy, improve market related incentives, encourage private enterprises, to reduce the role of the public sector by introducing ICT and Internet, developing digital economy. In order to understand the causal relationship between ICT investment and economic growth researchers have exert many effort in the world. The results are different: in developed countries the impact of ICT on economic growth is more powerful than in developing countries. This paper aims at finding and measuring causality between Economic growth and ICT development in emerging economies of Central Asian Countries by using panel data over the period of 19 years from 2000 – 2018. The research findings revealed that inflation, trade openness, final consumption expenditure and unemployment impact significantly on GDP per capita in Central Asian countries. The econometric analysis showed that ICT affects to GDP per capita positively and significantly: one percent increase in ICT contributes to GDP per capita 0.1669 percent (fixed broadband subscriptions) and 0.2218 percent (internet usage). Thus we concluded that information and communication technology together with economic indicators are key part of economic development in Central Asian countries. Reduction of inflation and unemployment allow expanding businesses, to create new job places in the digital economy.

Keyword : Digital, Economy, Responsibility

Subject :

[AR-0131]

**Factors Contributing To Prosocial Behavior Among Students
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Safrilsyah / Universiti Utara Malaysia),**

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0142 MOHD ZAILANI BIN MOHD YUSOFF)

UNIVERSITI UTARA MALAYSIA

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between religiosity, moral reasoning, internalization of pure values, and prosocial behavior. The sample consisted of 649 students from eight secondary schools in Banda Aceh. Samples were selected using a multi-stage cluster sampling technique. Data were collected using questionnaires. For this study, religiosity was measured using the SPPIM-R Secondary Islamic Education Internalization Scale (SPPIM-M) from Azma Mahmood (2006), moral reasoning was measured via Behavior Reasoning Scheme Indicator (UPSTA) (Aswati Hamzah, 2007), pure values appreciation was measured using the items for the appreciation of pure values (Mohamad Khairi Othman, Asmawati Suhib, Abdullah Mat Rashid & Samsilah Roslan, 2011) and prosocial behavior was measured using the Prosocial Tendencies Measure (PTM) scale developed by Carlo, Mestre, Samper, Tur, and Armenta (2010). A total of 649 religious and general secondary school students in Banda Aceh, Indonesia were involved in the study. Quantitative data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 23.0 version. The findings showed that there was a link between religiosity, moral reasoning, and internalization of pure values with the prosocial behavior of secondary school students in Banda Aceh. In conclusion, this study showed the level of religiosity, moral reasoning, and internalization of pure values influencing the prosocial behavior of secondary school students in Banda Aceh.

Keyword : religiosity; moral reasoning; pure values internalization; prosocial behaviors

Subject : Education

[AR-0043]

**Peer-Assessment Based Application In Teaching English Speaking
And Students' Perception Towards Peer-feedbacks
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Ronggolawe Tuban),**

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Abstract

In English as Foreign language country, students rarely find a contextual situation to speak English. They generally have few opportunities to communicate with people in English, not to mention to get feedback from others for making reflections. In the present study, students were situated in conversation with the virtual speakers. This application was applied to make them feel authentic English-speaking contexts. The peer assessment-based application was employed for guiding students to provide comments on peers' speaking performance and to make reflections on their own performance. In order to investigate the peer assessment, an online observation was conducted in English education study program online class. The online group interview was also done to recognize the students' perceptions towards the peer feedbacks. The study results reveal some steps done in doing the peer-assessment-based application in terms of the learners' English speaking including pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary and fluency. Moreover, it was found that the students can give assessment comprehensively to their peers. This study also analyzed the types of peer response by classifying them into four types: Compliment, Criticism, Opinion, and Irrelevant. The result of the study showed that that compliment feedback was helpful for the students' English-speaking performance, while Criticism feedback cause students' self-defense and did not motivate them to improve the speaking performance. Irrelevant feedback was not significantly correlated with the students' performance. In conclusion students have to think about their feedback before sending to their peers' performance.

Keyword : peer-assessment, application, speaking performance, students' perception

Subject :

[AR-0051]

**Representation Of Covid-19 Within Childrenâ€™s Cyberliterature
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Abstract

Since the Covid-19 Pandemic broke out, children's literacy has been carried out through digital media. Childrenâ€™s cyber literature (read: youtube) takes the opportunity as a way of delivering education about Covid-19. This paper is based on the assumption that Covid 19 is presented specifically in Childrenâ€™s cyber literature. Thus critical discourse analysis theory is relevant in unpacking issues within the literature issue. This theory draws on these suppositions to unveil how knowledge is constructed by stories or childrens. Critical discourse analysis will be used to analyze the choice of words, ways of delivery, and points of view presented to children. The results show that Covid-19 discourse is terrible and deadly, and can affect the future (death) of life so that it has psychological, cognitive and psychomotor impacts on children.

Keyword : covid-19 impact, children, childrenâ€™s cyber literature

Subject : Education

[AR-0022]

Analysis Of The Teaching Model For Professional Teacher Education (PPG) In The Position With Online System On The Mathematics Module Deepening Material

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Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the online learning model in the mathematics module deepening material for 30 PPG (Teacher Professional Education) learning participants in positions with an online system registered with PPG in the positions of Batch I, II, and III in 2020. Online learning models are divided into 8 sessions over 3 days or 400-minute lessons. The findings show that the participants still have difficulty learning the 1-4 learning activities mathematics modules which must be completed within the specified time. The lesson learned from this activity was that the participant's time management and additional practice questions could improve the final grade of learning. The positive impact obtained: 100% of participants stated that the difficulty in working on the questions was greatly assisted by the presence of media catting facilities and discussion forums. mastered (3) add to the literature.

Keyword : mathematics module deepening material, online system, teacher professional education.

Subject : Education

[AR-0084]

**CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY MODERATES THE EFFECT OF
FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE ON CORPORATE VALUE**

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Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to empirically examine the effect of financial performance on firm value and corporate social responsibility to moderate the effect of financial performance on firm value. The sample of this research is food and beverages companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2014-2018 which corporate social responsibility disclosure and financial reports respectively. Data analysis in this study using SmartPLS software. The results showed that financial performance had no effect on firm value and corporate social responsibility was able to moderate the effect of financial performance on firm value.

Keyword : corporate social responsibility, financial performance, firm value

Subject :

[AR-0096]

Photocatalytic Degradation Of Phenol Using TiO₂/Fe Under H₂O₂ Presence By UVVisible Light Irradiation

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Universitas Pakuan

Abstract

This research investigated photocatalytic degradation process of phenol using a TiO₂-Fe catalyst under halogen irradiation and additional H₂O₂. The effect of various conditions process was applied, including different catalyst doses (0.1; 0.2; 0.3; and 0.4 grams of TiO₂-Fe to 500 mL of sample solution), pH (3, 6, 8, and 11), reaction times (60, 90, 120 and 150 minutes) and the presence of H₂O₂. The degradation process was studied at initial concentration of phenol 5 mg/l. This study has been decreasing phenol content (90,51%) with catalyst doses 0,3 g/ 500 ml, pH solution 11, reaction time 150 and H₂O₂ concentration 30% . This final phenol concentration after photodegradation was 0,47 mg/l and this result is below of government regulation as per Kep. Men LH No51/MENLH/10/1995 i.e. 0,5 mg/l and this process possible to remove phenol in aqueous such as industrial wastewater or other resources.

Keyword : TiO₂-Fe, Phenol, H₂O₂, Halogen-ray, photodegradation

Subject :

[AR-0041]

**Online Learning To Write Poster Texts With Characteristics Of
Health Care In The Covid-19 Pandemic Era**
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0330 Euis Karnengsih / SMP Negeri 5 Tuban),*

Correspondent author : (RJI-1-0054 Moh Muminin)

Universitas PGRI Ronggolawe

Abstract

Learning to write text is part of language learning. One of them is writing poster text. In the 2013 Curriculum, any learning, including learning to write poster text, needs to instill character education. The character that needs to be applied during the Covid-19 pandemic is the character of caring for health. This study aims to describe online learning to write poster text with health care character in the Covid 19 pandemic era which includes lesson plan, teaching material, media, and assesment. The method used in this research is descriptive method and applied research with the learning design proposed by Dick & Carey (1990). The finding shows, online learning on wrting poster text about health care in the era of the covid-19 pandemic with lesson plan, teaching material, media, and assesment was valid, practical, and effective.

Keyword : online learning, writing poster text, health care, the covid-19 pandemic

Subject :

[AR-0038]

**FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT USING SCORE
MARGINAL APPROACH: EMPIRICAL STUDY OF STATE-OWNED
ENTERPRISES**

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the factors affecting the financial performance of State-Owned Enterprises. This study contributes to the development of financial performance measures used in previous studies. The results of this research are useful for the management of State-Owned Enterprises to evaluate the past of financial performance. The key factors that affect financial performance in this study are capital expenditure, working capital, retained earnings, additional equity, earnings management, and the interaction of cash flow from operations with government subsidies. The data used in this research is secondary data based on audited financial reports. The results of this study found that the total key variables have a significant effect on the financial performance of State-Owned Enterprises. The implication of the results is that company management needs to pay attention to the strategies and policies associated with these variables to increase the financial performance. The originality of this research is mainly on the development of a financial performance measurement model that uses a marginal approach score.

Keyword : Financial performance, marginal score, and government subsidies.

Subject :

[AR-0033]

The Effectiveness Of Transfersome Gel From Pandanus Leaf Extract As A Healing Burns In White Rats

(AC-0180 Yulianita / Universitas Pakuan), (AC-0181 Yulianita *, Rini Ambarwati, Rani Meilana / Universitas Pakuan),

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Universitas Pakuan

Abstract

The use of natural ingredients as medicine continues to be developed and improved from time to time. One of the natural ingredients that have medicinal properties is pandan leaves (*Pandanus amaryllifolius* Roxb). Research on the pharmacology of pandan wangi leaves that has been carried out is regarding the efficacy of the ointment of the fragrant view of the leaf extract as a healing burns The results showed that the ointment containing 10% pandanus leaf extract could be effective as a burn medicine with a healing time of 13 days. The healing activity of burns on pandan leaves is caused by the presence of secondary metabolites in the form of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins and polyphenols. The results of the above research were then developed by reformulating the ointment of pandan leaves extract. The dosage form chosen is transfersome preparation with nanoparticle technology. Transfersome gel was chosen to increase drug absorption through the skin, so it is hoped that the burn healing process will be better. The test for burns was carried out using the Morton method using white Sprague Dawley rats as experimental animals. The research parameters consisted of the diameter of wound healing and the percentage of wound healing. The results showed that the transferome gel from pandan leaf extract has activity as a burn drug comparable to the patent drugs on the market. transfersome gel, fragrant pandan leaf extract, burns

[AR-0026]

Information Needs Among Indonesia

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Abstract

The incidence of COVID-19 increases rapidly in Indonesia from it discovered for the first time in March 2020. The high transmission of COVID -19 seems associated with insufficient prevention behavior among society. COVID 19 is still a new disease globally, so the information about this disease is still lacking. This, of course, affects people's knowledge, which will impact their preventive behavior. Information about the behavior of seeking COVID -19 information is needed for providing accurate information for the provider. Researchers conducted an online survey of 816 respondents throughout Indonesia who at least aged 18 years old. Respondents were asked several topics about COVID -19, of which ten questions regarding their information needs. Our data were analyzed using a chi-square test. We found a significant relationship between gender and information-seeking behavior in maps and information on mask use. Then we discovered that there is a meaningful relationship between age and seeking behavior for COVID -19 history. From the results of this study, it can be used as a reference for related parties in providing information on COVID-19, so that the information presented can influence knowledge that will improve community prevention behavior.

Keyword : COVID -19, information needs, behaviour

Subject :

[AR-0002]

Development Of Flipped Learning Based On Android For Elementary School

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Abstract

The need for information technology today in education is commonplace, one of which is cellular learning. The Reverse Learning Method (Flipped Learning) represents an emerging form of mixed learning, in which students can be customized online before class and then engage in customized classroom learning activities with peers and instructors. While the FL framework will be intuitively attractive, its design and implementation involve considerable complexity. The aim of this study is to develop an FL design model for primary schools that can systematically guide instructors or designers in creating the right mix of individual online lectures and collaborative face-to-face learning activities. By using predetermined methods for model development research, the initial model is theoretically built repeatedly and undergoes internal and external validation through model use tests, expert reviews, and field evaluations. Making learning devices that contain features for students, namely syllabus, learning materials, e-books, games, video lessons, student worksheets in addition there are also features for teachers, namely syllabus work, games, e-books, student worksheets and videos learning, while for parents is a feature to view assignments and grades.

Keyword : Flipped Learning, Android, Elementary School Education Technology

Subject :

[AR-0006]

Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) Method For Measure The Dominance Of Product Design Against Industry Criteria 4.0

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Abstract

The ease with which people make transactions in this digital age, poses a serious threat to business people who are still conducting conventional transactions. This applies to the bottled drinking water industry which is still dominated by small entrepreneurs. The study population is bottled mineral water products. Research data sources consist of secondary data and primary data. Data analysis techniques using Structural Equation Model (SEM), by testing the industry criteria 4.0 and the competitiveness of bottled drinking water and AHP to determine the dominant factors that influence. The results of this study are the R-square test value for the goodness-fit model with a value of 0.454 for competitiveness and 0.361 for product design so that the R-square is greater than what is needed, namely 0.261, from the influence between variables, the product design has a direct influence on competitiveness with a parameter coefficient of 0.609, and industry principle 4.0 for product design with a parameter coefficient of 0.601. By testing AHP the dominant factor in product design in the industrial era 4.0

Keyword : design product, industry 4.0, bottled drinking water brands products.

Subject : Industrial Technology

[AR-0008]

CURRICULUM MANAGEMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC PERIOD

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has abroad impact in education, especially in aspects of curriculum management. The curriculum is a learning plan conveyed by the teacher to students with certain time allocation. The online learning from home policy determined by the Ministry of Education and Culture during the pandemic requires simplifying the form of the curriculum. This study has two objectives: First, to find out how management is implemented in simplifying the curriculum applied by primary school principals during the pandemic. Second, what is the form of curriculum simplification? This research uses qualitative approach with a case study. This subject included the principal, curriculum vice- and teachers at primary schools in Sidoarjo. The results of this study concluded that the management applied included : problem identification, planning, organizing, coordinating, implementing, and evaluating. Meanwhile the form of simplification is to reduce basic competence and time allocation. It is hoped that the principal will be able to design the curriculum properly

Keyword : Curriculum Management, Primary School, Covid 19 Pandemic
Subject : Education

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